

FELLOWSHIP

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Chandannagar's City Vision Document

A citizen-led vision narrative capturing stories,
concerns, and hopes for the city's future

About the Vision Document

This City Vision Document is a reflective learning assignment carried out as part of the Nāgrika Fellowship Programme. It is based on a limited number of conversations with citizens and observational research conducted over a few months by the fellow. The document does not claim to represent the complete or official vision of the city, but rather offers a citizen-led snapshot—built through individual stories, insights, and lived experiences gathered during the fellowship. The perspectives shared here reflect the voices of a few residents, selected to capture a range of age groups, professions, and neighborhoods. The document is not exhaustive and may not include all communities or viewpoints. This document is intended as a starting point for dialogue and reflection. We hope it encourages broader conversations about the city’s identity, challenges, and future possibilities.

The research and writing were undertaken independently by the fellow, within a framework of structured guidance provided by Nāgrika. This included thematic prompts, narrative-building exercises, regular mentorship and feedback sessions, all designed to support the fellow in shaping their city’s vision. The interpretations and final content remain those of the fellow.

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Nāgrika Fellowship

The **Nāgrika Fellowship Programme** has been designed to empower young individuals from diverse educational and geographic backgrounds, including students, gap-year participants, and early-career researchers, to positively engage with the history, socio-economic, governance, and cultural context of their cities. Focused on the youth of small and mid-sized cities, the fellowship is building local knowledge, enabling civic consciousness, and developing thought leaders who can address environmental, social, and infrastructural challenges. Over a period of six months, fellows gained tools for understanding and engaging with their cities.

A key component of the fellowship is the development of the **City Vision Document** by the fellows. This document is an emotionally grounded reflection of how citizens experience and imagine their city. Developed through conversations with diverse residents of the fellows' cities, it weaves together stories of everyday life, places of belonging, pressing concerns, and aspirations for the future. The document captures lived experiences and heartfelt insights to build a narrative that is authentic, accessible, and community-driven. It serves not only as a record of local voices but also as an invitation to reimagine the city through the eyes of those who call it home.

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Everyday Life

This theme explores the daily rhythms, routines, and interactions that shape how people experience their city. It highlights the ordinary yet meaningful details of our city's life and how citizens connect with their surroundings on a regular basis.

Places of Belonging

Places of Belonging are spaces that hold emotional, cultural, or social significance for residents. This theme focuses on spaces that provide identity, memory, and a sense of home, the places where we feel connected, seen, and grounded.

Voices of Concern

This theme brings out the issues and challenges that citizens face in their day-to-day lives such as poor infrastructure, lack of public transport, disappearing green spaces, water or waste management issues, safety concerns, or loss of cultural heritage.

Dreams for Tomorrow

Dreams for Tomorrow reflects citizens' aspirations for the city's future. This theme brings forward ideas, hopes, and solutions imagined by the people who live in and care for the city.

Acknowledgement

This City Vision Document is the result of many conversations, shared experiences, and collective reflections. While I have authored this document, it is by no means mine alone.

I would like to express my deepest gratitude to the Nāgrika team for creating the space and opportunity to undertake this work. I am especially thankful to the founders, Yutika Vora and Tarun Sharma, whose vision and guidance shaped the entire direction of this project. Their commitment to citizen-led urban thinking has been a constant source of inspiration. I am equally grateful to Praisy David and the extended Nāgrika team for their support, feedback, and encouragement throughout the process. I appeared before you as a small-city girl, hopelessly in love with my city, but with no way to express it. Your guidance and curation have given me the vision to channel my love into an actionable form.

I am especially grateful to my fellow members of the Nāgrika Fellowship 2025-26 Cohort for their warm friendship, honest input and jovial community spirit. Representing your own cultures from different parts of the country, you have taught me hands-on how to find unity in diversity. It was an honour and a privilege to learn so much from each one of you. Everyone's unique insight helped me in some part of completing this document.

I owe a special debt of gratitude to all the residents of Chandannagar who generously shared their time, stories, and insights with me. From friends and family to shopkeepers, teachers, homemakers, professionals, municipal representatives, and active citizens—each conversation added depth and meaning to this document. Your honesty, warmth, and willingness to reflect on your city made this work possible.

I would also like to thank those who agreed to be interviewed despite their busy schedules, including community members, local representatives, and others who offered perspectives from within the systems that shape the city. Your inputs provided invaluable context and nuance.

My sincere thanks to the reviewers and mentors who took the time to read, critique, and refine this document. Your feedback helped sharpen both its structure and its intent.

I am grateful to everyone who contributed photographs, visual material, and other resources that helped bring the narrative to life. I especially thank photographer and citizen historian, Mr Indrajit Dey, for not only generously permitting me to use his pictures, but also sharing additional materials to enrich this document. I thank my friends who, in the course of this project, have continuously sent visual materials and information about anything going on in the city. These contributions have made the document richer and more grounded in our collective lived reality.

On a more personal note, I would like to thank my parents for their constant support and encouragement. Their belief in my work has sustained me throughout this journey. I am also deeply thankful to my friends again for listening, discussing, debating, and standing by me during the making of this document.

Finally, I acknowledge the city of Chandannagar itself—its people, its histories, its contradictions, and its quiet resilience. This document is, above all, an attempt to listen.

Why this Vision Document?

যদি কাগজে লে খো নাম কাগজ ছি ঁড়ে যাবে
পাথরে লে খো নাম পাথর ক্ষয়ে যাবে
হৃদয়ে লে খো নাম সে নাম রয়ে যাবে ...

*[If you write your name on paper, the paper will tear.
Write your name on stone, the stone will wear away.
Write the name in your heart, that name will remain...]*

(Jodi Kagoje Lekho Nam, Gauriprasanna Majumder)

Every city tells a story, but not everyone gets to write it. Too often, urban narratives are shaped by planners, policymakers, or external observers who see the city from above through data, maps, and master plans. These perspectives matter, but they are incomplete. So many stories of smaller cities remain in the heart, not for lack of love, but because people believe informal conversations are enough to preserve them. They seldom appear as data or are recorded on paper. The deeper story of a city lives in its streets, its homes, its everyday negotiations in the lived experiences of the people who inhabit it. I believe that the residents are the most qualified authors of their city's story. They are the ones who have witnessed its transformations over time, who understand its contradictions, and who carry within them grounded, practical ideas about where it should go next.

This document, therefore, is not just a record. Rather, it is an assertion of voice and agency. It recognises that knowledge about the city does not only reside in institutions, but in the collective memory, observation, and imagination of its people. By bringing these voices together, it challenges the idea that cities are shaped only from the top down. Instead, it positions citizens as active participants in defining the future who are capable not just of identifying problems, but of envisioning solutions.

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At the same time, every city is held together by an underlying thread—a shared sense of identity that exists even before it is articulated. The pride in the revolutionary legacy of Chandannagar, love for the Strand, community participation in Jagaddhatri Puja, the nuanced relationship with the city’s French colonial legacy, a shared love of Jolbhora and overall nostalgia for an era past unite the residents of Chandannagar. Whatever form it takes, this collective identity shapes how people relate to one another and to the city itself. This document is an expression of that identity. It does not create it, but makes it visible, attempting to name the values, relationships, and ways of being that already bind the city together.

Finally, the purpose of this City Vision Document is to materialise a vision. It compiles some of the concerns that often remain unspoken, whether about infrastructure, governance, environment, or social life and tries to pin the underlying pattern causing such concerns. It showcases aspirations that may otherwise go unheard—ideas for a more inclusive, functional, and vibrant future. It offers not just critique but hope. It invites both citizens and decision-makers to pause and listen. I hope it sparks constructive dialogue.

In creating the document, I found that the people who know this city best are not waiting to be acted upon, but are ready to act. This document is, ultimately, an invitation: to see the city differently, to imagine it collectively, and to actively listen to the voices that have always been at its heart.

Meet Chandannagar

“Paris is a huge homesick peasant,
He carries a thousand villages in his heart.”
(Paris: *A Poem*, Hope Mirrlees)

City is probably not the first word that would come to mind for a resident of Chandannagar to describe this charming place. We find it much more comforting to describe it as a small town, an hour away from the “real” city of Kolkata. However, by all legal criteria, Chandannagar, with its own Municipal Corporation, is a city, no matter how one feels about the tag (Chandannagore Municipal Act 1990). The city has a three-hundred-year-old, nuanced history that directly affects many aspects of contemporary life here. Residents are proud of the city’s heritage, and maintaining that legacy is of great priority to them. The history is almost as important as the geography, climate, culture and nature of the city in informing the very identity of the citizens of Chandannagar.

Chandannagar seems like an unassuming city on the western bank of the Hooghly River, but it has more layers than it lets on. Residents of the city know it by many names— Farasdanga, Chandernagore, and Chandannagar. The word “Chandernagore” probably comes from the beautiful crescent-shaped turn of the Hooghly, which flanks the city; “*Chand*” meaning moon and “*nagore*,” a western spelling of “*nagar*” meaning city (Seth, II, 4). Literally, “Moon City,” Chandannagar is probably a bastardisation of Chandernagore. Look at the river from the beautiful Strand, and you will see yourself at the centre of the moon.

Again, some residents believe, the city received its name from the “*Chandan*” or white sandalwood sold here during the colonial era (P. Roy). A flourishing trade in articles like lac, wax, saltpetre, cane, timber, sandalwood, textiles, silk and spices, and cottage industries producing textiles, silk, *sola*, conch-shell articles, as well as the French-established jute mill at *Gondolpara*, made Chandannagar an important trade centre in those days (P. Roy). Another opinion is that the city received its name from the deity of the goddess *Chandi* worshipped for centuries at *Borai Chanditala*, which even finds mention in the works of Bengali poet Bipradas describing the voyage of *Chand Sadagar* written sometime in the fifteenth century (Seth, 195). Both origins tell a story: the first of the city’s commercial importance, and the second about the antiquity of the place.

The first name, *Farasdanga*, has the clearest etymological origin; it literally means French Land—a nod to the distinctive colonial past of the city. Chandannagar, similar to Kolkata, was formed by European traders as a trade post along the river by combining the three villages *Borokishanpur*, *Khalisani* and *Gondolpara*. The French East India Company obtained permission from Ibrahim Khan, then Nawab of Bengal, to establish a trading post here in 1673, and by 1688, it had become a permanent French settlement.

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One of the most important European settlements along the Hooghly River, Chandannagar was once a larger commercial centre than British-ruled Kolkata. It maintained trade relations with Basora, China, Pegu, Jedda, Tibet, etc., but gradually lost its position to Kolkata, which, being further downstream, was more convenient for maritime trade (District Court Hooghly). Although Chandannagar changed hands several times, particularly between the French and the British, who were engaged in wars during the period, it remained under French rule until 1950.

India earned its independence from British rule on 15th August 1947, but alas, Chandannagar was still a French colony! Chandannagar was, however, the first among the few French territories of India, including Pondicherry, to gain freedom. On 19th June 1948, a formal mass plebiscite was organised for the residents of the city to decide whether to stay on as a French colony or join the Indian Union. An overwhelming 97% of the population voted to merge with India. 2nd May, 1950 marked the de facto transfer of administration by the French to the Indian government, while the de jure transfer happened on 9th June, 1952. Chandannagar was officially integrated into the state of West Bengal on 2nd October, 1954 (“Chandernagar”). The people of the city still carry with them the pride of choosing their identity and the fate of their city.

The early exit of Chandannagar from French India can be attributed to the geographical isolation of the city from other territories like Puducherry, Karaikal, Mahe, and Yanam. However, the town had always been a hotbed of nationalist and revolutionary movements. Even now, you can see the *Prabartak Sangha*, established by revolutionary leader Motilal Roy, initiated by Sri Aurovindo in 1920, where India’s freedom fighters, including Rashbehari Bose and, as local legend has it, even Subhas Chandra Bose, gathered to hide from British forces (Chakraborty 662).

Today, the name *Farasdanga* only exists in informal conversations and stories, though the city itself still carries on the blend of Indo-French legacy through its everyday existence. French is still offered as a third language option in most schools of the city; one of the most prestigious government schools, *Kanailal Vidyamandir*, has an entire French section; roads have French names, such as Rue de Carnot; the Duplex Palace is now the *Institute de Chandernagore*, and Chandernagore College have a thriving French department. The architecture of other old buildings like the Sacred Heart Church, Clock Tower, Registry building, Court and even the current premises of the Chandannagar Municipal Corporation Office still carries the colonial grandeur.

Chandannagar is by no means a city stuck only in its colonial roots, and has developed a unique identity for itself beyond its colonial legacy. One of the most important yearly traditions of Chandannagar is the Jagaddhatri puja festival, annually celebrated around October or November all over the city and its neighbouring regions: *Mankundu* and *Bhadreswar*.

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While there are disagreements regarding the actual origin of the puja in the city, residents agree that the oldest community worship of the Jagaddhatri goddess idol was established approximately 300 years ago at *Chaulpatty* at *Laxmigunj Bazar*. Robert Clive had called *Laxmigunj bazar*, a still thriving market in present-day Chandannagar, the “Granary of Bengal” due to the sheer amount of grain bought and sold there (Wikipedia). By the first half of the twentieth century, many *barowaris* had adopted the Jagaddhatri puja, and now it is a city-wide week-long festival. Aside from theme pandals and light shows typical of such festivals, the USP of the Jagaddhatri puja at Chandannagar is the gigantic idols of the goddesses, the tallest reaching a height of more than 35 ft.

Jagaddhatri Puja is now more than a Hindu festival; it brings together community participation from people of all religions, classes and professions in a harmonious celebration of festive spirit. For example, the 42-year-old Padripara Puja Committee organises the puja in the land owned by the local mosque, Imtiaz Hussain bears the cost of the idol, and Christians Joseph and Anna Biswas share all the responsibilities of the puja. Joseph Biswas, in conversation with ETV Bharat, said, “I have been associated with this puja since childhood. My father was also associated with this puja. We Hindus, Muslims and Christians all worship here (“Chandannagar’s Jagaddhatri Puja...”). The five days of the puja, Chandannagar transforms into a land of magical illumination and festivity, welcoming tourists in the lakhs and generating significant informal income through temporary vendors and shops setting up business here.

The final *Dashami* night of the festival is another crowd puller: the show-stopping procession of these idols around the city and through the Strand on lorries decked up in Chandannagar’s own festival lighting. Pioneered by inventors like Sridhar Das and Babu Pal, the festival lightmaking industry of Chandannagar is a major economic and cultural contributor to the city. Combining art and technology, Chandannagar’s festival lighting is revered all over the world, and the night-long procession during the Jagaddhatri puja is almost a moving exhibition of the creativity and artistic innovations of the lightmakers. Visitors during the time are dazzled by the sheer grandeur of the small city, and residents believe that the city transforms into a magical place during the time.

Chandannagar is a small city in terms of area, and an athletic person can easily walk from one end of the city to the other. Being a part of the Gangetic floodplains, the land is fertile, and the western peri-urban part of the expanding city is still an agricultural land where mango, banana, bamboo, and other seasonal crops are cultivated. Bananas are a popular export of this area, and locals know them to be of particularly good quality. Fish is also cultivated in many of the small ponds and lakes spread throughout the city, and some informal fishing is done in the Hooghly River as well.

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The residents of Chandannagar are a mix of old and new. The city is part of the area covered by Kolkata Metropolitan Development Authority (KMDA), and it is extremely easy for people to commute daily to Kolkata via an excellent local train service and smooth road connection. Many residents of Chandannagar work or study in Kolkata and do not feel the need to move to the metro city to avail such opportunities. In terms of transportation out of the city, there is also a public ferry service to cross the Hooghly River. Their after-work social routine is concentrated either in the iconic Strand or the many local tea and snack shops at neighbourhood corners.

Chandannagar is a lived-in city: cosy and suburban, but still dynamic. While the Chandannagar Municipality was founded back in 1880, it was upgraded to the Chandannagar Municipal Corporation in 1994 according to The Chandernagore Municipal Corporation Act, 1990, to include the western part of the city in response to urban growth and rising civic needs. Expansion has continued both horizontally and vertically with the construction of new houses and high-rise apartments. Many commercial brands have found their markets in the growing city and capitalised on rising populations to open franchises in Chandannagar. While you will find a thriving and long-standing street-food culture and local business scene in the city, this recent boom allows you to eat at a restaurant like Karim's or shop at a Pantaloons or a Zudio just as easily.

Chandannagar is currently a city at a crossroads between old and new, antiquity and modernity, tradition and innovation, development and neglect. It is a city in transition with a rich history, a vibrant present, and many hopes and dreams for the future. It is a city that no longer wants to remain the quiet suburban riverfront town others know it as; it is a city with its own identity and personality that is on the brink of demanding to be heard.

State	West Bengal
District	Hooghly
Population	166,867 (2011 Census)
Area	~ 16-20 km.sq
Type of City Government	Municipal Corporation
Languages prevalent	Bengali, Hindi, English, French

PHOTO GALLERY

Image: Capture de Chandernagore en 1757 par la Royal Navy, by Dominic Serres, the Elder, Public Domain

Image: Kanailal Vidyamandir Section Française

Image: Jagaddhatri Puja at Chaulpatty in 2025

Image: Jagaddhatri Puja crowd at Bagbazar

Image: "Magical" light gates lining the Palpara Road

Image: Dasami procession at the Strand

Meet Citizens

Consider the lives of Dupleix-da and Bimala-di, a married couple raising a family in the city. Dupleix-da, named after Joseph François Dupleix, the Governor-General of French India, credited with the development of the city into a major trade hub, steps onto the riverfront of Chandannagar at 7:00 am. The morning air is still soft, and the Strand is already dotted with walkers, joggers, and familiar faces. For him, this is less about exercise and more about connecting to his city.

Not far away, inside their home, Bimala-di, the namesake of the protagonist from Rabindranath Tagore's *Home and the World*, is already busy with domestic work. By 8:00 am, Dupleix-da is in Laxmiganj bazar, moving through a dense but familiar web of vendors and customers. He pauses at familiar stalls, bargaining lightly, catching up on local news. By 9:00 am, he drops his daughter off at school and then navigates traffic toward Chandannagar railway station. At 9:30 am, he boards a crowded train to Howrah to reach his office in Kolkata—his day now tied to a larger urban economy beyond the town.

Meanwhile, Bimala-di is at her doorway, handing over blue and green buckets of segregated waste to the waste collector. This routine connects her to the formal systems operating within the city. Like many women of Chandannagar, she is left at home while her husband and child leave for work and school, respectively. As they leave, the house becomes quieter, and she gets a much-needed respite. A little later, at 10:00 am, she settles into her verandah with a newspaper, exchanging comments and observations with neighbours across balconies and thresholds. Information, here, travels as much through conversation as through print.

At 10:30 am, Bimala-di steps out to buy fish from a mobile vendor pulling a rickshaw van. The transaction is quick but familiar, shaped by routine and trust. By 11:00 am, she is back home cooking—her work largely invisible in the public life of the city, yet central to sustaining it.

Their days unfold in parallel. While Dupleix-da spends hours commuting and working outside, Bimala-di's labour is rooted within the neighbourhood, punctuated by errands, care work, and moments of social exchange. By afternoon, at 3:00 pm, Bimala-di leaves to pick up her child from school, sitting in a *toto*. The streets briefly fill again with parents and children before settling down.

By 6:30 pm, Dupleix-da returns, stepping off onto platform 2 (or 3) at the station with a familiar crowd. He rides through busy streets, heading home, dodging vehicles with practised efficiency. Around the same time, Bimala-di transitions from the day's tasks to the evening's slower rhythm. At 7:00 pm, Dupleix-da reaches home, greeted by his family. Domestic space becomes a shared ground where their routines intersect—his return from outside work and her continuous presence within the home.

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Later in the evening, Dupleix-da heads to a local tea stall for adda, joining friends in conversation that drifts across topics and concerns. Earlier, Bimala-di had taken a different kind of pause—walking her dog along the footpath, occasionally stopping to feed biscuits to stray dogs. Occasionally, she too meets up with friends and family at spaces like the Strand, goes shopping or hops cafes. Her interactions, quieter but no less meaningful, reflect another way of inhabiting public space.

By 9:00 pm, Dupleix-da rides back through quieter, tree-lined streets. The city slows down, shedding the urgency of the day. By 10:00 pm, he sits down for dinner with his family, where Bimala-di's earlier labour culminates in a shared meal.

Dupleix-da and Bimala-di do not represent all citizens, but together they reveal complementary rhythms of life in Chandannagar. His day stretches across the town and the metropolis, shaped by mobility and wage work. Hers is rooted in the neighbourhood, structured by care, domestic labour, and informal networks. Their lives intersect in the home, but extend into different yet interconnected spheres—showing how the city is sustained not by one kind of routine, but by many, layered together.

Image: A day in the life of the fictional Dupleix-da and Bimala-di. Visuals created with the help of AI.

INTRODUCTION

I have lived in Chandannagar my whole life, and loved most moments of it. The old houses, the new brands, the occasional French tourist, the chirping of returning birds at sunset, the people stopping mid-commute to say hello: they all make up the Chandannagar I know. When I paused to listen to the city, many voices emerged that both agreed and disagreed with my own. I began by interviewing the people in my circle, my friends, and my family. Coming from various walks of life, they revealed aspects of the city that were both familiar and unfamiliar to me. Some of them were government employees, some teachers, some engineers, some homemakers, some domestic workers, some students and so on.

Then I connected with active citizens who really endeavour to make the city livable and lively. Among them were authors, activists, members of puja committees and others. Most people were elated to get to speak about their experiences living in the city once I assured them that I was not looking for expert opinions. They candidly spoke about their everyday lives, places of belonging, concerns, and hopes and dreams about their city in relation to their personal lives. Through mutual connections, I managed to interview important people of the everyday fabric of life at Chandannagar, like doctors, shopkeepers, senior citizens, artists, etc. Lastly, despite the busy election season, a few councillors and ex-councillors agreed to speak about their experience of Chandannagar and provided a backstage view of the workings of the city. This City Vision Document is my attempt to collate the real voices of the people of Chandannagar, who really live in and interact with the city, and present a cohesive document of its past, present and future.

Image: Location of Chandannagar City and its administrative wards. (The top right image shows the Chandannagar Municipal Corporation (CMC) boundary before 1994, and the bottom right image shows the CMC boundary after 1994). Ghosh, Pritha & Singh, Kiran. (2021). Spatiotemporal dynamics of urban green and blue spaces using geospatial techniques in Chandannagar city, India. *GeoJournal*. 87. 1-18. 10.1007/s10708-021-10524-0.

Glossary and Local Terms

TABLE 1: GLOSSARY & LOCAL TERMS

Word or Phrase in Regional Language	Translation in English
<i>Barowari</i>	Neighbourhood community
<i>Chalchitro</i>	traditional, rounded background frame of idols for puja
<i>Chand</i>	Moon
<i>Chand Sadagar</i>	A sea merchant of Champaknagar who is one of the principal characters in the Bengali medieval poem "Manasamangal Kāvya" (or "Manasa Vijay") written by Bipradas Pipulai
<i>Chandan</i>	White sandalwood
<i>Chandi</i>	A demon-destroying form of the Hindu goddess Shakti, particularly popular in eastern India. She is known by various names, such as Mahamaya ("Great Magic") or Abhaya ("She Who Is Without Fear"). Her representation is similar to that of Durga, another form of Shakti. She is shown with either 8 or 10 arms, seated on a lion vehicle. Hundreds of folktales and songs tell of her exploits. She is the central figure of an extensive medieval Bengali literature known as Chandi-mangal, the most famous of which is that of Mukundarama Chakravarti (c. 16th century). (source: Brittanica)
<i>Chaulpatty</i>	
<i>Dashami</i>	Grain market
	Literally "tenth." The tenth day of any Hindu luni-solar calendar month. Here, on Dashami, the city bids farewell to the Goddess. The day is defined by the grand immersion procession of Chandannagar, a spectacular parade of art, light, and devotion, symbolising the Goddess's return to her abode.
<i>Ekadashi</i>	Literally "eleventh." Here, the day

Glossary and Local Terms

TABLE 1: GLOSSARY & LOCAL TERMS	
Word or Phrase in Regional Language	Translation in English
	after the Dashami, when the Jagaddhatri idol is actually immersed in the Hooghly river.
<i>Hooghly or Hugli</i>	A district of West Bengal on the western bank of the Hooghly River
<i>Hooghly River</i>	A major distributary of the River Ganges flowing from Murshidabad to the Bay of Bengal
<i>Jagaddhatri</i> [জগদ্ধাত্রী :ঐ]	Jagatdhatri or Jagaddhatri or Mahadurga (lit. 'Bearer of the World') is an aspect of the Hindu goddess Durga, worshipped in West Bengal and other states like Odisha and Jharkhand. In Bengal, her puja is celebrated as the comeback of Devi, specifically in Krishnanagar, Chandannagar, Santipur, Rishra, Midnapore, Singur and Guptipara.
<i>Jolbhora</i>	Literally meaning “water-filled.” Here, a type of Bengali sweet with liquid, usually rosewater or jaggery, is injected into it. It is a speciality invented by Surya Kumar Modak of Chandannagar and is an iconic sweet of the area.
<i>Nagar</i>	City
<i>Para</i>	Neighborhood
<i>Sola</i>	A traditional eco-friendly material derived from the Indian cork plant or pith plant, used by artisans of regions of Bengal to make auspicious ornaments for pujas and special occasions like weddings
<i>Toto</i>	e-rickshaw

Everyday Life

Everyday Life

Morning in Chandannagar begins with a slow assembling of movement. Walkers move in familiar practised patterns along the Strand—some in silence, others in quiet conversation. Tea stalls open in increments, their first customers already known to the shopkeeper. By 8 AM, the rhythm shifts. Streets leading to the station begin to fill, e-rickshaws weaving through pedestrians, schoolchildren navigating the same roads as office-goers. The city compresses into urgency, only to release itself again by afternoon, when shutters half-close and the heat settles in. The great Indian summer casts a tiring haze of blazing sunlight over the city. In winter, though, the afternoon is a place for lively neighbourhood conversations as homemakers and school children on vacation soak in the sun, and yell out mundane cosy conversations between verandahs and terraces. By evening, Chandannagar returns to itself, so do the commuters. The same streets that carried commuters now host conversations. People gather without planning—at tea stalls, at crossings, along the Strand. Nothing monumental happens on typical days, yet the repetition of these moments gives the city its texture. It is in this cycle that residents locate their sense of belonging.

The very first person I interviewed, an engineer who had moved to Chandannagar when he was a school student, described the city’s daily atmosphere as “full of life and spontaneity.” In subsequent interviews, I noticed similar observations. The vibrant social life of Chandannagar, which is most visible during the week of the Jagaddhatri puja, subtly permeates all aspects of Chandannagar’s daily existence. From morning walks on the Strand or neighbourhood fields like Mary field, to evening adda sessions with childhood friends in neighbourhood tea stalls: Chandannagar is constantly buzzing with activity. But for much of the population, interaction with the lively city happens only during their daily commute.

The morning rush starts at around 8:00 am and continues till 10:30 am. The streets around the station tighten—totos cluster at entrances, pedestrians move in quick, calculated paths, and the urgency of catching a train reshapes the pace of the city. The evening rush is more periodic; it happens in waves as trains, the principal vehicle of daily commute for most residents, bring groups of residents back to the city. You can easily tell when the recent train has arrived based on the traffic conditions within the city. Office-goers, school children, college and university students, teachers, patients seeking medical assistance, local businesses, small vendors, hawkers, all depend on the Eastern Railways for their travel to and from the city.

The Chandannagar Station has been selected to be upgraded as a model station under the Amrit Bharat Station scheme, and much of the work has already been completed. Yet, the inherent position of the Station causes a bottleneck effect on traffic, especially during rush hours, which often causes delays in the commuters’ quest to catch their trains.

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A citizen during the interview pointed out the illegal toto stand at one of the entrances that frequently causes issues with traffic flow. While there is an overbridge connecting the two platforms of the Station and an underpass, a daily commuter complained that the underpass is difficult to navigate due to insufficient lighting and waterlogging during the monsoon season. The lucky part is that trains are mostly frequent and regular, ensuring excellent connectivity to Kolkata via Howrah or other urban centres like Bandel or Bardhaman. If policymakers understood the impact of this traffic situation and the importance of the commute via the train through the Station, they would implement better and stricter rules to regulate traffic, especially during the rush hours in the Station complex and invest in maintaining or creating alternative entrances to the Station.

Image: Chandannagar Station

The station and the railway track bifurcate the city into the older urban eastern region and the newer and expanding western region. The British did not receive permission to construct the station inside the French-occupied area and had to construct it beyond the official limits of the city. For years, the underpass at the Station was the main link between the two parts. Only small vehicles (under 6.5ft in height, about that of a Tata Sumo) could go through, meaning large trucks like those carrying construction materials had to take 20 km long detours through Baidyabati or Mogra to enter the eastern part of the city from the Delhi road. The Chandannagar Flyover, inaugurated in 2016, was a game-changer for how Chandannagar moves as it connected the Grand Trunk Road and the Delhi Road via a 2.5 km road and a 750 m bridge over railway tracks, farmland, and residential areas (“Bridge to Change”). The limitation that history had inflicted on Chandannagar was finally solved by the development of the bypass road. Now, even common residents who travel out of the city via car breathe a sigh of relief as they do not have to get caught in the rush hour traffic snarl of the city. Informally, this has also increased the scope of drivers-on-hire and resulted in more private car ownership in Chandannagar. The heavy traffic load on the Station Road and the underpass has also been reduced significantly if you are just passing through. Still, entering the Station remains an issue. However, this development gives hope to the residents that policymakers are understanding of the problem that has existed in the city since the inception of the Chandannagar Railway Station in 1854.

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The western region was only added officially to the city in 1995 as six new wards with the upgradation of the Municipality to Municipal Corporation. A former councillor of the Purosree region recounted the necessity of this change: “Our ward had reached a point of saturation. It had become necessary to move from one system to another. And I used to see back then, for these six wards, only ₹2 lakhs or ₹3 lakhs used to come. The Panchayat system was like that. At that time, we thought, if we could bring a new kind of development, would development expand?” The saturation he mentions has continued to affect other areas of city life as well. A citizen historian pointed out that because resources were earlier concentrated in the eastern part of Chandannagar, urban growth was also concentrated within a walking perimeter from the public amenities. He says, “People have to build houses, and land isn't available in Chandannagar anymore. As a result, further west, since the communication system is comparatively much better now, roads are much clearer than before; this [expansion] is increasing westward. No problem with that... The communication system nearby, shops, getting essential items nearby, getting medical treatment, doctors, medicine – the closer these are, the more important the place is. Now these are becoming available everywhere. And since now, if you need something, you can order it online, and it arrives. So, these factors aren't as crucial. Arranging a shelter for oneself is crucial.” The connection improvement between the two parts of the city is slowly reducing the problems of uneven access to resources that people of both parts previously faced. However, the wards 28 to 33 are not covered under the Chandannagar Police Station's jurisdiction yet, but instead under the Bhadreswar Police Station, which is further away. The consensus now is that Chandannagar has almost all the urban amenities that a person needs to function, and therefore is a welcoming city that encourages people to settle down here. If policymakers understood the positive effect of efficient transport, communication and connection between parts of a city on all aspects of residents' daily lives, they would look towards implementing a similar solution in other areas as well.

Road or Station Road, which remain the most important road of Chandannagar, connecting it to the outside world. The population increase has increased to vehicles as well. There are abundant e-rickshaws, or totos as they are locally called, which are available to ferry passengers from one place to another without fixed routes. Autos move on specific routes. Earlier, the Private no. 2 buses ploughed through the Grand Trunk Road connecting Chandannagar via road to Chinsurah and Srerampore. However, the bus service was discontinued during the pandemic, and though the residents believe that there is a plan to restart it, the plan has not been implemented yet. For most residents, the best options to commute in the city are by toto or by private two-wheelers. Residents believe that travelling within the city is convenient enough, but some, including senior citizens, highlight the difficulty in walking compared to earlier, due to the excessive number of vehicles. The unpredictability of these informal modes of travel is also a grave issue for those who depend solely on them. An elderly domestic worker revealed her daily struggles with commuting to and from the locality she works in during our conversation: the twenty-rupee one-way toto fare adds up, and the vehicles themselves are scarce during her morning hours, all congregating instead at the station to ferry commuters.

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Her return journey at three in the afternoon presents its own ordeal—scorching heat in summer, deserted streets, and tuk-tuk drivers who demand more to navigate the alley to her home. Her schedule becomes precarious, dependent on her son's irregular driving shifts for an occasional ride, and her work rhythm must flex around these uncertainties. If policymakers understood that livelihoods depended on the predictability of transport, they would work on solutions such as implementing standardised fares or routes to ensure equal connectivity all over the city.

Women interviewees did not mention any gender specific safety or mobility issues in Chandannagar, even when probed, and some even exclusively denied any inconvenience. A woman in her 20s stated that she feels safe to roam most parts of the city by herself even after midnight. Another young private tutor said that since she has a very busy schedule, she prefers to walk the Strand after 10 at night to unwind and faces no difficulty in doing so. Older women respondents, in contrast, remembered spending their childhood and youth confined within their own homes due to contemporary social norms. They too noted and appreciated the freedom that girls and women are now able to enjoy within Chandannagar.

In an entirely positive note, residents all over Chandannagar unanimously praised the door-to-door waste collection system as well as the overall cleanliness of the city in recent years. The Chandernagore Municipal Corporation Solid Waste Management Bye-laws 2024 have been implemented and enforced with great effect and work through the collaborations of waste generators, i.e. residents and businesses, and the CMC. The auto-tippers and vans manned by waste collectors with shrill whistles move within each ward to collect segregated waste from residential properties. They refuse to collect unsegregated garbage, eliminating the possibility of non-compliance. The elimination of open public dustbins has been a blessing to the hygiene of the city.

Image: E-rickshaws at the Chandannagar Strand Road

EVERYDAY LIFE

Though according to popular public demand, the Strand Road has very recently been provided with waste-segregation bins for the use of the public, as it is a public space with a huge footfall. This attention to case-by-case demand and need is highly appreciated by the residents of Chandannagar, as revealed in the interviews. The Bhagar landfill, where all waste from the city was eventually dumped, was a grave and hazardous issue, causing foul smells and affecting the health of residents living nearby. Recently, the CMC has obtained some land away from residential areas to act as a new landfill while simultaneously implementing recycling initiatives through tenders (“Chandannagar Civic Body...”). Chandannagar’s residents have started breathing better as the plan is carried forward.

As the door-to-door waste collection has become a formal routine of the city, the door-to-door vendors are a part of the informal routine of many. A homemaker in the Bagbajar area confessed that she obtains items for her daily needs from the comfort of her own home and praises the convenience of mobile vendors. This saves her ample time, though she agrees that the practice is costlier than going to the Laxmiganj bazar. She becomes a part of the informal economy system operating throughout the city. The platform economies, like online daily essential delivery services that are a relative newcomer to the region, with Bigbasket starting operations first in 2025 and others following, compete with these already existing networks of local mobile vendors with established rapport and familiarity. Old shopkeepers echo this feeling of security in the loyalty of the community they are a part of. A Laxmiganj bazar shopkeeper proudly declared that his rented shop has survived at least four ownership changes of the building, and he feels sure that it will outlast these online platforms as well. These shops and even some mobile vendors have evolved with the age, and most of them make use of digital payment services like UPI for the use of their customers. Many shops, especially pharmacies, have locally started offering delivery services, which are indispensable to many elderly residents or residents having mobility issues who live alone. If policymakers understood the deep-rootedness of these informal commercial interactions in small cities, they would promote and preserve local mechanisms of purchase and sale and allow them to coexist with the newer mechanisms.

Image: A typical vehicle used for door-to-door waste collection in Chandannagar.

EVERYDAY LIFE

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What emerges from these everyday moments is a city defined not by scale or speed, but by continuity and familiarity. Chandannagar is experienced as a place where life is repetitive but meaningful, where the ordinary is not empty but full of small interactions that accumulate into belonging. The comforts of the city include strong neighbourhood familiarity and social recognition, a reliable train and road connectivity to Kolkata and nearby towns, efficient waste management and improved cleanliness, easy access to daily essentials through both formal and informal systems and so on. But everyday life in Chandannagar is not without its own share of frictions: traffic congestion and bottlenecks during rush hour at specific areas, increasing difficulty of pedestrian movement, pressure on local vendors from digital platforms, etc.

Chandannagar is constantly developing, and this development is changing the everyday life of its residents for better or for worse. These everyday patterns are shaped by the city’s historical layering and spatial structure. The railway line, originally placed outside the French settlement, continues to influence mobility and congestion. The east-west divide reflects earlier uneven distribution of resources, while recent infrastructural expansion is gradually redistributing access. Informal systems—totos, mobile vendors, adda spaces—persist because they are flexible, adaptive, and socially embedded in ways formal systems are not.

Chandannagar works because its systems—formal and informal—are closely intertwined with lived habits. Yet, these same systems are fragile. Traffic congestion, unpredictable transport, platform economies, and uneven development are not just infrastructural issues—they reshape how people experience time, movement, and interaction in the city. If policymakers understood this, they would realise that improving everyday life in Chandannagar is not only about infrastructure, but about preserving the conditions that allow informal, social, and localised systems to function. Managing traffic at the station, supporting small vendors, and ensuring pedestrian-friendly mobility are not isolated interventions—they directly shape how people experience belonging in the city.

নভাগোপাল স্মৃতিমন্দির
চন্দননগর পুস্তকাগার

Places of Belonging

Places of Belonging

Belonging in a city is rarely abstract—it is anchored in places where life unfolds in habitual, intimate, and meaningful ways. Based on interviews and observations, Chandannagar emerges not merely as a geographical entity but as a lived archive of memory, relationships, and shared rhythms. Its places of belonging range from iconic public spaces to quiet domestic interiors, from bustling festive grounds to fading institutions. Together, they reveal how identity is spatially produced and emotionally sustained.

The Strand, running along the Hooghly River, is perhaps the most iconic public space in Chandannagar. Lined with trees, colonial-era structures, and benches, it opens onto the river, offering both visual relief and social possibility. The central Joraghat functions as a quieter extension—less formal, more intimate. Across interviews, the Strand emerges as a shared civic space cutting across age, class, and gender. Elderly residents walk here at dawn; couples and young people gather in the evenings; families visit during festivals. Historically, the Strand dates back to the French colonial period, embedding it deeply in the city’s urban memory. Many interviewees recall visiting it since childhood, marking it as a transgenerational space. The Strand is not just a promenade—it is a stage of everyday life. For some, it symbolises continuity; for others, it is where friendships, romances, and family rituals unfold. It represents a shared identity tied to the river.

A youth from the city declared in one of the interviews, “I cannot think of Chandannagar without its Strand. It's probably the best public space there is in the district. It's the very essence of the city. Losing this place would be like losing the city itself.”

The Strand feels welcoming to all, but at the same time, some residents feel that visitors do not care for the place. A political party worker highlighted the darker side of the rising popularity of the Strand due to its value on social media: “If the tourists have no respect for the place, how will we residents be able to welcome them? Rather than a blessing, they have become a nuisance.” Overcrowding during peak hours and festival times also alters its accessibility. Development here should be careful because this place carries the layered memory of a city’s public life, accessible to all and welcoming.

The overcrowding at the Strand during special occasions may be because it is the most accessible and well-known feature of the city. Measures have been taken by the CMC to curb and regulate the crowd by enforcing it as a “Green Zone”, meaning vehicle parking is not allowed on the Strand road. Alternative Parking spaces have been constructed, which are accessible and used by many. The Police also enforce a complete cutoff of vehicle movement in the area during special occasions to ensure the safety of pedestrians. The visitors to the Strand generate considerable income for the vendors and stalls at the Strand, which have been assigned designated commercial spaces.

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Many of these vendors have been operating their business here for generations, and some have regulars over multiple generations of the same family. There is a community toilet open all hours of the day near the Parking space, which is maintained semi-regularly. There are two public parks for children, and even basic exercise equipment for adults. The Strand is a mixture of old systems that keep working and new developments to make life easier. But development here should be careful because the balance between the Strand's historical significance and its modern use as a vibrant social hub must be maintained.

While change is inevitable, many residents of Chandannagar feel a general loss of the city's unique culture, heritage and character. Some credit it to the influx of people coming from different places with their own culture who refuse to adopt or adapt to the local culture. For many interviewees, belonging is rooted not in public landmarks but in private, familial spaces—ancestral homes, courtyards, or a relative's house. Families use these spaces for daily life, rituals, and gatherings. They often extend beyond nuclear units to include neighbours and kin. These spaces are often inherited, carrying generational continuity. A senior citizen of Lalbagan proudly declared that his grandson is the fifth generation living in the same house. Home is described as the primary anchor of belonging. It is where identity is first formed and sustained.

Urban development, migration, and changing family structures (nuclearisation) are reshaping these spaces. The communities of Chandannagar have always felt tight-knit with locality-level clubs, puja committees, festivals and so on. However, these places are welcoming primarily to insiders—family and close networks, whereas “outsiders” are often left feeling isolated. Particularly striking was a conversation with a homemaker, a woman who had moved to Chandannagar with her family fifteen years ago and still feels extremely isolated as the residents of her neighbourhood intentionally leave her out of social and community events simply because her family did not have a multigenerational existence there. While her husband and daughter have opportunities to form connections and social interactions at work and school, respectively, she feels that her only place of belonging is her home. In contrast, an elderly homemaker reminisced about how she was embraced by her in-laws' neighbourhood when she had arrived in Chandannagar as a newlywed bride some forty years back. But she notices that her daughter-in-law is a homebody and is not friends with anyone of her age in the locality. She does not blame her, but observes how people of the next generation are retreating inwards. She says: “There are so many people now in Chandannagar, but so few to talk to.”

However, many older residents also expressed their disappointment with the self-isolation of newcomers and harbour an antagonistic view of what they term “flat culture” as a replacement of the safer “para culture.” Residents of such newfangled apartment complexes have also expressed significant criticism of “flat culture” from their own point of view. An artist who had moved to the city twenty years ago bitterly shared his experiences of dealing with uncooperative neighbours, isolation from existing neighbourhood communities and the shabby condition of built-for-profit apartment buildings that have mushroomed all over the city.

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Image: Apartment buildings in Chandannagar

Image: Rakshit Bhaban, a heritage building conserved and maintained under a trust. A branch of the family still lives in the mansion, and it is open to visitors during specific pujas.

Image: Demolition of Seth Mansion at Bagbazar. Picture by Indrajit Dey.

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He encouraged new buyers to conduct a thorough examination of the property they are buying, including whether it's up to code, the reputation of the seller or developer, and so on, before making the significant investment. Development here should be careful because the home and the locality are the primary place of sustenance that carries intimate histories that cannot be replicated, and are the primary spaces for any resident to exist comfortably.

Many old houses in Chandannagar are being sold to promoters as the owners are financially incapable of maintaining these spaces. One such example, which was a point of discussion in Chandannagar in early 2026, was the Sett family's Bagbazar mansion being demolished. As citizen historian Indrajit Dey says, "The condition for the survival of historical buildings in Chandannagar is, if it is under a trust, they will survive. For example, the house of Durgacharan Rakshit has a trust; they maintain it. And those which are not under a trust, due to [family] disputes and the lure of easy money from promoters, most of them are being sold off. Another reason is that it is not possible for ordinary people to maintain them. Maintaining an old historical house properly costs several hundred times more than maintaining an ordinary house, which is almost impossible."

Many of these mansions, under private ownership, feature in the rich history of the city and Bengal, through associations with notable residents and their architecture. In 2010, conservation architect Aishwarya Tipnis, working with the French Consulate for several years, compiled a list of 99 buildings, including both public and private ones, that needed restoration within the city. According to Tipnis, these buildings are a combination of French and Bengali architectural styles, unlike the entire French architecture found in other French colonies. The European exterior leads into a Bengali-style courtyard for almost all of these houses. According to a 2019 article on *The Hindu*, officials of the Heritage Commission of West Bengal have said that 14 buildings in the city have been declared as heritage properties including the Liberty Gate, House of Harihat Sett, Rakshit Bhawan, Liberty Gate and both the English and French sections of the Kanailal Vidyamandir, Thistle Hotel, Clock Tower, Church of Sister Cluny and French Cemetery Cathedral (Singh).

Though the State Government and the French Consulate have shown interest in the restoration and conservation of many of these buildings, the matter of procuring the required funds remains. There have been community engagement projects like "The Heritage & People of Chandernagore" aimed at finding meaning and relevance of the city's shared cultural heritage, and many citizen historians work towards preserving the history of these spaces, while preserving the space itself still remains a difficulty. Development here should be careful in preserving the history of the city and must work with, not against, the antiquity of these buildings, which physically record the unique history of the city in their brick and lime walls. This history, in turn, gives identity and pride to the residents of the city.

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For some residents, their favourite place of belonging is more abstract than physical. A college professor who confesses that he has spent his entire conscious life in Chandannagar says: “Since I grew up here consciously, my school friends—especially childhood friends—and the mental space associated with them is my most comfortable space, a space of emotional comfort. They are always there, and with them I can speak openly. They are just like me; they grew up the same way I did, with the same type of culture and mentality. That is my sense of belonging.” The sense of community, familiarity and stability informs his feelings of belonging. On the other hand, a woman in her 50s gave a heartfelt description of her connection to Chandannagar: “I am not from Chandannagar by birth, yet after coming to Chandannagar, I felt Chandannagar has accepted me as its own. I mean, the people of the neighbourhood here, the surrounding neighbours, then later... After that, much later, when I started music, I saw this cultural world, I mean, it embraced me very warmly, and I really like this cultural world. The various cultural practices of Chandannagar, I really enjoy them and I feel this is like my place.” For her, the practice of music came with a community and a sense of belonging. Other residents also echoed a similar feeling about the cultural world of Chandannagar, concentrating on communities based on hobbies and cultural practices like art and gardening. Development here should foster and encourage these local hobby-centred clubs and communities, and work with them to establish the community feeling that seems to be slipping from the urban consciousness.

Image: Jagaddhatri Puja pandals

Image: Bagbazar Jagaddhatri Puja Committee members and volunteers hauling the Jagaddhatri idol onto the truck in preparation for the procession

Temporary yet recurring, neighbourhood puja spaces—especially during Jagaddhatri Puja—transform streets and localities into vibrant cultural hubs. In Chandannagar, these are not confined to a single field or square; rather, entire streets, para (neighbourhood) crossings, and open plots are temporarily reimaged through bamboo frameworks, fabric canopies, elaborate lighting installations, and sculptural idols. The spatial transformation is immersive—lanes that ordinarily facilitate mundane circulation become sites of spectacle, devotion, and gathering. Residents actively participate in organising, decorating, and attending these festivals. These spaces foster collective labour and shared celebration.

Many interviewees trace their association with these spaces to childhood, suggesting decades-long continuity. Festivals act as “social glue.” They create belonging not through permanence but through repetition. Identity here is performative and communal. However, as a volunteer of a reputable puja committee pointed out, rising costs, commercialisation, and competitive aesthetics (theme-based pujas) risk overshadowing community participation. She gives an example, “Every puja committee now has a professionally recorded theme song. Earlier, we only had chants that everyone from a toddler to a grandfather could hum, and the healthy competition between the committees was there. Now it's all about who secures greater sponsorship, and there is naturally an air of putting on spectacles and appearances that comes with that.”

Earlier, most pujas were entirely crowdfunded, but now they depend on additional sponsorship from corporations and brands. Increasing sponsorships, prize competitions, and media attention have shifted the focus from community participation to spectacle. Some interviewees expressed concern that “theme” and scale are beginning to overshadow intimacy and local involvement.

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Interviewees repeatedly emphasised that Jagaddhatri Puja is not something one merely attends—it is something one does. Young men and boys are often involved in construction, decoration, lighting arrangements, and logistical work. Many described staying up all night in the days leading up to the puja, forging friendships through shared labour. Women participate through ritual preparation, cultural programs, and increasingly in organisational roles—though some noted that leadership still tends to be male-dominated. Elderly residents often take on advisory roles or simply observe, finding continuity with past celebrations. The concept of Sabeki saj, or old-fashioned and traditional adornment of the idols, is a debated topic every puja.

Traditionally, eco-friendly and artisan-made sola (made from Indian cork or pith plant) ornaments were used, and there was a particular style of making the idol that is still followed in most pujas of Krishnanagar, from where Chandannagar’s puja tradition traces its origin. Many committees have moved beyond this and developed styles of their own. For example, the Jagaddhatri idol of Helapukur was adorned entirely in diamonds. Even the chalchitro (traditional rounded background frame of the idol) was made entirely of diamonds in 2025. Development here should be careful to maintain the delicate balance of tradition and innovation to preserve the Jagaddhatri puja as a space for social participation while leaving it ample space to grow and evolve.

Image: (left to right) an idol with exquisite traditional sola adornments; “art” idol which is considered a modern innovation; idol of the Helapukur Jagaddhatri Puja Committee adorned entirely in diamonds

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Visitors from outside the city—and even from other districts—arrive as spectators, particularly drawn by Chandannagar’s famous lighting displays. This creates a layered experience: insiders who build and belong, and outsiders who witness and admire. It is also a great boost to the city’s economy as vendors from far and near set up stalls here. The lightmakers also find exposure, almost treating the festival as a gallery to display their work, and even sponsor certain puja committees as a way of giving back to the community. The Chandannagar Central Jagadhatri Puja Committee (CMC and West Bengal Police work well in tandem with each other to manage the festival. With No-Entry hours, vehicle passes, temporary toilet set-ups, police checkpoints, help stations, special train services and so on, the residents believe that the authorities do a good enough job of managing the event. However, the days before the festival is a chaotic time for the city as the footpaths and roads become encroached with bamboo structures, vehicles carrying materials for the pujas ply through the city, roads suddenly start being repaired and so on.

As mentioned earlier, the typical Jagaddhatri idols are two to three-storey tall, meaning they were at risk of hitting high-voltage overhead wires while moving through the city. Earlier, electricity would be shut off for safe movement of the idols through the city on Dashami for the procession, and the following Ekadashi, where the idols were to be actually immersed in the Hooghly River. 2025 was the first year that residents did not experience any break in electricity supply, having completed a major power infrastructure revamp, replacing over 450 km of overhead electrical lines with an underground cabling system costing ₹ 120 crore to the state (The Statesman, 2025). This move was welcomed by the residents who had adapted to the two-day-long electricity break, having experienced it for generations. Mindful and localised development here thus proved that tradition does not have to be sacrificed for comfort, safety and efficiency.

Image: Jagaddhatri Puja light gates at Bagbazar

Image: Volunteers holding up high-voltage cables (electricity turned off) for the tall idols to pass unharmed. A common scene before the switch to underground wiring in 2025.

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Image: A light-decorated truck participating in the Jagaddhatri Puja Dashami procession at night

Image: A toy seller at Laxmiganj bazar

The Chandannagar Central Jagaddhatri Puja Committee was established in 1933, transforming the festival from a collection of individual 'para' (locality) pujas into a unified, centrally-managed event of immense scale and grandeur. As a volunteer of a reputed puja committee bitterly pointed out, the State has tried to co-opt the Chandannagar Jagaddhatri Puja and especially its procession on Dashami night, which is currently completely free to attend and goes around the entire city, in multiple ways.

There have been efforts to make the event a ticketed and exclusive event like the state-run Durga Puja carnival at Red Road, Kolkata. This has been met with city-wide opposition, especially on social media, as what they love most about the puja is its inclusivity and accessibility. With 70+ participating Puja committees and around 250 vehicles decorated in light and carrying the idols, marching bands, cultural dances and spectacular road performances, the grand night is something that cannot be recreated. Development here should be careful because this place carries an intangible cultural heritage rooted in both participation and spectacle, inclusive of all and free to celebrate.

Moving to more everyday places of belonging, scattered across neighbourhoods, small shops and markets function as everyday nodes of interaction. Residents visit daily—for groceries, tea, or casual conversation. Shopkeepers often know customers personally. The bigger markets like Laxmiganj bazar or Boubazar form the commercial heart of the city.

These are spaces of familiarity and trust. They anchor routine and provide a sense of continuity in a changing urban environment. Development here should be careful because this place carries the micro-social fabric of the city.

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Once vibrant reading rooms and community hubs, Chandannagar’s libraries like the Chandannagar Pustakagar and Kalidas Pathagar are now quieter, often underfunded spaces surviving due to the efforts of a few dedicated common people. Older generations recall them as spaces of intellectual engagement—reading newspapers, borrowing books, and socialising. Today, usage has declined significantly. For many, these libraries symbolise a lost era of collective learning and cultural refinement. They are tied to nostalgia and intellectual identity. Digital media, lack of funding, and changing reading habits have rendered these spaces fragile. A young school teacher bluntly confessed that her place of belonging was College Street in Kolkata, where she could buy the latest books at discounted prices, as she felt that the libraries in Chandannagar were unable to stock contemporary books despite being state-owned. She admitted that she would gladly visit the library if she could access the latest books there and pointed out that there are many booklovers still in the city based on her observation of the crowds at the annual Chandannagar Book Fair.

There are at present 4 public libraries in the city with a combined member strength of only 7,578. These libraries jointly own 1,16,815 books (“Library”). The infrastructure exists, but the usage of such infrastructure is another issue altogether. The Chandannagar Pustakagar shares its identity with the Nritya Gopal Smriti Mandir, which is an event space for cultural programmes and frequently stages art, theatre and scholastic debates.

The intellectual atmosphere is still vibrant here, but library use remains minimal. Stocking new books, digitising existing collections, digital subscriptions to journals and magazines, etc., might boost membership in an age increasingly dependent on the internet. Development here should be careful because these libraries carry the intellectual history of the city, now at risk of erasure.

Image: Chandannagar Pustakagar, a public library and the Nritya Gopal Smriti Mandir. Picture by Indrajit Dey.

PLACES OF BELONGING

Less visible but equally significant are ponds, reclaimed lands, and quiet neighbourhood corners. These spaces are used informally—for relaxation, children’s play, or solitary reflection. A college student revealed his favourite places in the city: “There’s no particular place of belonging for me as such. I like being in nature. So, if I had to tell you the name of a space, then I would say either the tree-laden road leading up to Delhi Road near Byajra or the green spaces and ponds near the Nabagram side.” Often longstanding but undocumented, these spaces exist outside formal planning narratives. They represent alternative forms of belonging—less performative, more personal and introspective. Encroachment, neglect, and real estate development threaten their existence. Development here should be careful because these places carry subtle, everyday attachments often overlooked in urban planning.

Belonging in Chandannagar is not singular—it is layered, shifting between public and private, permanent and seasonal, visible and hidden. The Strand offers a shared civic identity; festivals create cyclical belonging; libraries embody intellectual memory; markets sustain everyday interaction; homes anchor emotional life; and marginal spaces provide quiet refuge. However, these places are not equally accessible. Questions of inclusion—who belongs, who feels excluded—run through all of them. Commercialisation, urban development, and changing lifestyles are reshaping these spaces, often eroding the very qualities that make them meaningful.

To preserve Chandannagar’s sense of belonging, development must move beyond infrastructure and aesthetics. It must recognise that these places are repositories of memory, identity, and social life. Any intervention should be careful, participatory, and sensitive to the intangible values embedded within it. Because ultimately, a city is not just built of roads and buildings—it is built of places where people feel they belong.

Image: Mango orchards towards the outskirts of the city

Voices of Concern

Voices of Concern

The interviews reveal a city negotiating multiple, overlapping anxieties—some rooted in long-term structural neglect, others emerging from rapid socio-economic transformation. Rather than isolated complaints, these concerns cluster into broader patterns that point to systemic weaknesses. Across generations and social groups, residents express unease about the erosion of infrastructure, institutional reliability, and community life. At the same time, these concerns are not experienced uniformly: youth articulate frustration over limited opportunities, and older residents reflect on the disappearance of long-standing institutions, many of which have been run by the same families for decades.

A consistent concern across interviews is the deterioration of basic infrastructure—roads, drainage, and public transport. Respondents describe a city where everyday mobility has become increasingly difficult. Infrastructure is experienced daily; its failures are immediate and visible, making it one of the most frequently cited concerns. This concern persists because maintenance remains reactive rather than preventive, and long-term planning is inconsistently executed. The effects are cumulative: longer commute times, increased physical strain, and reduced productivity. For working professionals, unreliable transport translates into lost work hours, while for elderly residents, poor roads and pavements limit mobility altogether.

Beyond general infrastructure decline, a more specific and frequently articulated concern is the breakdown of traffic regulation and enforcement. Respondents describe roads not simply as congested, but as disorderly spaces where rules are inconsistently followed and rarely enforced. Issues include illegal parking, unregulated toto movement, encroachment by vendors, lack of functioning traffic signals, and minimal presence of traffic personnel at key junctions. Together, these create an environment where mobility is shaped less by formal rules and more by informal negotiation.

Image: A long-unrepaired portion of the Strand

VOICES OF CONCERN

The fate of the aforementioned elderly domestic worker's struggle to commute to work despite the abundance of totos, because toto-drivers refuse to ferry a single person through alleys that are not hotspots, is shared by many residents of the city. For working professionals and daily wage earners, unpredictable travel times translate into lost income, missed opportunities, and increased stress. The absence of clear lane discipline and pedestrian infrastructure exposes residents to frequent near-accidents. A young woman complained during our conversation: "Chandannagar is absolutely horrendous for biking around now. The excessive traffic, especially totos are infuriating. I recently met with an accident at Jyoti when I was returning from doing some errands... Thankfully, I only suffered a bruise to the ligament and only needed some rest. It could easily have been something more. Here, one problem is excessive traffic. But, the other equal problem is a lack of civic sense." Elderly respondents describe avoiding busy intersections altogether, while parents express concern about children commuting to school or tuition. Idling vehicles in congested areas contribute to air and noise pollution. Respondents also indirectly link traffic stagnation to declining environmental quality, especially in densely populated neighbourhoods.

The traffic issues' persistence lies in its normalisation—citizens adapt to it, even as they continue to critique it. A key pattern is the normalisation of informality. Many respondents acknowledge that while they are frustrated by rule-breaking, they also participate in it when necessary—parking in restricted areas, crossing roads arbitrarily, or relying on informal transport practices. This reflects a broader adaptive response to systemic gaps. If there are no convenient pedestrian amenities, pedestrians are bound to break rules. The same goes for vehicles.

Another pattern is the perceived absence of authority. Even when traffic personnel are present, respondents feel enforcement is selective or inconsistent. This perception weakens the legitimacy of rules themselves, reinforcing a cycle where compliance appears optional. An active citizen with ties to the CMC, when questioned about whether there have been measures taken by the local government to regulate traffic, especially totos, revealed that there were efforts to implement a registration process for e-rickshaws like those implemented in other municipalities like Bolpur or Behrampore, but they were ultimately resisted after a union of e-rickshaw drivers raised the issue in court. He called for a nationwide standardisation of rules and regulations for such transportation, which normally does not require licenses and acknowledged how, without such efforts, the roads of small cities like Chandannagar are growing extremely overcrowded and disorderly.

One of the most emotionally charged concerns emerging from the interviews is the rapid commercialisation of urban space and its impact on the city's historical and cultural fabric. Respondents repeatedly describe a landscape in transition: long-standing establishments are closing, relocating, or being replaced by standardised commercial outlets. What is being lost, in their view, is not just physical architecture but an entire ecosystem of memory, identity, and everyday cultural practice. A resident in his 50s lamented the loss of the tailoring shops due to the growing favorability of readymade clothes.

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A quieter, yet historically significant loss for locals of Chandannagar is the loss of the once iconic handloom Farasdanga dhoti, as artisans grappled with the declining demand and advancement of technology, rendering the handloom industry obsolete.

The concern is not framed as opposition to development per se. Rather, interviewees express unease at the form development is taking—often unregulated, aesthetically incongruous, and detached from local context. The result is a city that feels increasingly interchangeable with others, losing the distinctiveness that once defined it. The erosion of heritage is experienced gradually but accumulatively.

Each closure or redevelopment may appear isolated, but over time, these changes produce a visible and effective shift in the urban environment. This concern persists because economic pressures favour redevelopment, regulatory frameworks for heritage protection are weak or inconsistently enforced, and planning processes rarely incorporate community voices. Residents frequently link heritage spaces to personal and collective memory.

Old shops, houses, and public spaces serve as anchors of identity—places where social interactions unfold and histories are embedded in everyday life. Their disappearance produces a subtle but profound disorientation: familiar landmarks vanish, altering how people navigate and relate to the city. There is no *Das Bakery*, the iconic historic bakery of the city, now to anchor the location at *Barabazar*, a chain bakery with two other outlets in the city itself stands in its place.

Image: A traditional handloom used to weave Farasdanga dhoti, now on display at Chandannagar College Museum

Image: A traditional handloom used to weave Farasdanga dhoti, now in display at Chandannagar College Museum

VOICES OF CONCERN

Image: Brands at a Commercial Market

Respondents repeatedly describe a shift toward uniformity. New commercial establishments—chain stores, modern retail spaces—are perceived as interchangeable and disconnected from local culture. The Baazar Kolkata eats into the business of the old Sreehari Garment shop, only a few minutes away. The old mansions with their unique pillars and arched windows cannot be maintained by private funding and are one by one giving way to boxy apartment buildings. This homogenization has broader implications: it reduces the uniqueness of the city as a cultural and historical site; it diminishes its potential for heritage-based tourism; it weakens emotional attachment among residents. A significant pattern is the tension between nostalgia and pragmatism. While many respondents mourn the loss of heritage, they also acknowledge the economic realities driving change.

A former councillor expressed his disappointment at the fact that annual ward meetings are no longer conducted by any of the current municipal representatives, nor is there sufficient active participation of common people to create pressure on the government as compared to before. A shift from active civic engagement to passive resignation is becoming evident, particularly among younger residents, a concern raised by several residents over multiple interviews. Repeated experiences of unaddressed grievances create a cycle of disillusionment. Incidentally, the public feels a general alienation from the decision-making processes as development happens without citizen input regularly. Cases such as repairing roads that do not need repair while ignoring ones that do are a waste of the authorities' time and resources, as well as a point of great frustration for the people who continue to walk those broken roads. On the other hand, aspects like waste management, especially the door-to-door waste collection, have been praised almost unanimously by the residents for realising their vision of a clean city.

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Without citizen input, such projects are bound to be hit-or-miss. The authorities responsible for Chandannagar seem to be looking at development as an end to make a developed city and not a means to improve the quality of life of the people.

Additionally, some sections of the residents hold themselves accountable for not taking an active enough part in shaping the city. Neither is their input taken into account, nor are they encouraged or enabled to share their input in an actionable manner. Residents feel that redevelopment occurs without meaningful consultation, reinforcing the perception that urban change is imposed rather than negotiated. Frustration with governance emerges as a pervasive theme. Respondents frequently describe a lack of responsiveness, transparency, and accountability from civic authorities. However, residents of Chandannagar notice that the maintenance of public infrastructure like the Strand is not a problem that arises from the authorities' lack of effort alone. Rather, they hold both the authorities and the general public dually accountable for the state of its facilities. Chandannagar is ultimately a city which has to be lived in by people who plan to continue their existence in the city for the foreseeable future. By excluding the residents from the city-shaping processes, Chandannagar risks becoming a city that is alien or incompatible with the people living here.

Governance failures amplify other issues—poor infrastructure, inadequate healthcare, and environmental neglect. Citizens increasingly rely on private solutions, normalising systemic inadequacies and deepening inequalities. A significant anxiety revolves around the lack of accessible, well-equipped healthcare facilities. Residents repeatedly highlight the need to travel long distances for emergency care. While the Chandannagar Sub Divisional Hospital exists, serving both urban and rural populations of the region, residents of the city, including a doctor, emphasised that the same shortcomings that plague other government healthcare facilities, like underfunding or understaffing, also plague this hospital.

Most interviewees describe a fragmented and uneven healthcare landscape, where basic services may exist but comprehensive, reliable care—especially in emergencies—is difficult to access. The issue is not only geographical distance from advanced facilities, but also the lack of trust in existing local options, perceived shortages of trained personnel, limited diagnostic infrastructure, and inconsistent availability of medicines and emergency support. However, older residents pointed out that healthcare options in Chandannagar had improved a lot over the years, pointing to the Ankur Hospital in the neighbouring Bhadreswar municipality and private nursing homes such as Dr Dutta's Clinic and New United Nursing Home in the city.

Several respondents emphasised that while small clinics and pharmacies are present, and there were several eminent and talented doctors in the city, they often function as stop-gap solutions rather than dependable care providers. In serious situations—cardiac events, accidents, or complications during childbirth—residents must travel to larger urban centres, introducing critical delays.

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Additionally, healthcare concerns tend to repeat because they intersect with multiple other systemic gaps: economic disparities limit access to private care, which is often the most reliable kind of care available in a city like Chandannagar. In the absence of reliable public healthcare, those who can afford it turn to private hospitals in nearby cities. This creates a two-tier system: middle- and upper-income families rely on costly private care, and lower-income groups delay treatment or depend on inadequate local options.

A recurring and deeply reflective concern across interviews is the gradual weakening of community life. Respondents describe a shift from a socially cohesive environment—marked by familiarity, mutual support, and shared public life—to one characterised by increasing isolation, anonymity, and reduced interpersonal engagement. This transformation is not attributed to a single cause but emerges from intersecting changes in lifestyle, urban form, and social values. Importantly, this concern is often articulated through comparison: residents contrast the present with a remembered past in which neighbourhoods functioned as tightly knit social units. While this memory may be partly idealised, it nonetheless reflects a widely shared perception that something fundamental has changed in how people relate to one another. However, there is a sharp divide in the responses of people who have grown up here and people who have moved here in more recent years. While the first group is able to pinpoint a time in the city itself when community life was spontaneous and lively, the members of the second group often expressed a feeling of isolation from the very beginning. They had antagonistic views of each other, both blaming the other for the perceived unwelcoming attitude from each other.

Social fragmentation is not immediately visible in the way that infrastructure or traffic problems are, but it is experienced in subtle, everyday ways—fewer conversations, reduced participation in community events, and a general sense of emotional distance. Because it unfolds gradually, it is often recognised retrospectively, making it a persistent and recurring theme in reflective accounts. This concern persists because changing work patterns, increased mobility, digital modes of interaction, and the decline of shared public spaces reduce opportunities for sustained, face-to-face social engagement.

Traditionally, community networks have functioned as informal safety nets—neighbours assisting during emergencies, sharing resources, or providing emotional support. As these networks weaken, individuals become more dependent on formal systems, which are themselves perceived as unreliable. For elderly residents, this shift is particularly significant. A homemaker in her 70s noted that “earlier, help was just next door—now you feel like you have to manage everything on your own.”

A fragmented community is less able to mobilise around shared concerns. Several respondents implicitly link social fragmentation to governance gaps, noting that collective action—petitions, neighbourhood initiatives, or civic engagement—has declined.

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A former councillor expressed his observations, “Nowadays, it's what you can call a social malaise, people have withdrawn themselves. They remain silent. Be it due to livelihood pressures, some unfulfilled needs, problems with their children, or maybe their children's unemployment and so on.” This creates a reinforcing cycle that sustains and feeds itself.

A key pattern is the paradox of proximity without connection. As the city becomes more densely populated, opportunities for interaction theoretically increase, yet meaningful engagement declines. Residents live closer together physically but are more socially distant. Another pattern is the intergenerational divide in perception: older residents emphasise loss and nostalgia while younger respondents often accept fragmentation as a norm, even as they express dissatisfaction with it. Moreover, the public spaces like the Strand are more accessible to the youth, most of whom eagerly describe it as the social heartbeat of Chandannagar. Elderly residents due to constraints of mobility often cannot access such spaces and rely on occasional local and neighbourhood gatherings like pujas for their social interactions.

Community events—particularly large, historically rooted festivals like Jagaddhatri Puja—emerge in the interviews as complex sites of both cohesion and change. Respondents consistently identify such events as central to the city's cultural identity and collective life. However, they also note shifts in how these events are organised, experienced, and valued. What was once a deeply community-driven, participatory practice is increasingly perceived as more spectacular, competitive, and externally oriented.

Rather than disappearing, community life is being reconfigured—and festivals like Jagaddhatri Puja sit at the centre of this transformation. A major shift identified in the conversations is the movement from active community participation to passive consumption. As mentioned earlier, residents note that Jagaddhatri Puja has become increasingly competitive, with emphasis on larger budgets, elaborate lighting and decorations, and theme-based installations. While this enhances visibility and attracts visitors, it also shifts focus away from local participation, religious or cultural meaning and smaller, neighbourhood-based pujas.

Image: A large-scale Jagaddhatri Puja idol during the Dashami procession

Image: Visitors crowd on the Strand to witness the Dashami procession

VOICES OF CONCERN

There is an intergenerational divide in the perception of the festival: older residents emphasise loss of intimacy and community spirit, while younger participants engage more with the spectacle, social media, and mobility aspects. The CMC and the Chandannagar Central Jagaddhatri Puja Committee work in collaboration with the puja committees to organise and manage the huge crowds of spectators during the festival, and most respondents expressed praise for their dual coordination and management capabilities. Respondents also recognised the economic benefits, like temporary employment of vendors, decorators, transport providers, etc., increased business for local shops and so on.

Most respondents consider the implemented “No-entry” rules that do not allow vehicles (without passes issued by the police) to travel within the city, generally implemented from afternoon to midnight during the festival week, as necessary and welcome. Some, like a resident who moved here a few years ago, declared: “During Jagaddhatri Puja, my wife and I roam around the city on my bike. The No Entry cannot stop me anymore because I now know all the shortcuts! I guess that is the mark of a true Chandannagarian.”

However, some elderly citizens who have mobility issues and rely on vehicles like e-rickshaws for moving around the city expressed a little disappointment at not being able to hop pandals as before, but ultimately, most confessed that they prefer to see the idols in the day anyway, when the crowd is less, and the vehicle movement is allowed. Walking becomes the only mode of transport during the evening at the time, though the insiders who know the checkpoints where police are situated can easily roam the city on two-wheelers, evading the rules.

Image: No Entry signage and traffic personnel stationed at Bagbajar Court More during the Jagaddhatri Puja

VOICES OF CONCERN

Another concern highlighted by several residents and articulated best by a youth is that: “There are too many pompous celebrations nowadays. Earlier, only the Jagaddhatri Puja was being organised with grandiose arrangements, and that too for a maximum of four days. Now Jagaddhatri Puja has been extended to a week. Moreover, I am seeing that every puja is becoming a festival. After Saraswati Puja, this year, there were hundreds of processions for two whole days. While I understand that this is good for circulating money within the city and displaying the iconic Chandannagar festival lights, and perhaps even drawing in tourists, the local people are generally more annoyed than happy. Processions mean disrupted traffic all over the city. And so much noise. There's seldom peace now.”

Overcrowding on special occasions at the Strand is also an issue raised by a few passionate residents of the city. As the Strand remains a free, accessible and beautiful social spot, and has been popularised even more through social media, tourists flock in huge numbers to the Strand to the point of overcrowding. There are more public spaces in the city, the newest one being the Laldighi park, which has been recently beautified and redeveloped, but most remain unused and empty. Many residents of the city expressed surprise that the Laldighi park was open and free for the public when I asked them about it.

The perception of the park is also skewed due to its proximity to a slum area, but personally, when I visited, I found the park well-maintained and peaceful. Without announcements or advertisements that the park was welcoming visitors, it has failed to register as a renewed social public space in the consciousness of the residents.

Image: Laldighi

VOICES OF CONCERN

A prominent and often emotionally charged concern across interviews is the perceived disengagement of youth, frequently framed alongside anxieties about changing values, behaviour, and aspirations. This issue is articulated in two distinct but overlapping ways: older respondents tend to interpret it as a decline in discipline or “misconduct,” while younger respondents describe a lack of meaningful opportunities, guidance, and institutional support. Rather than a singular problem, this concern reflects a broader disjunction between expectations and realities.

Youth are navigating an environment where educational attainment does not necessarily translate into employment, and where avenues for creative, professional, or civic engagement remain limited. A young man who believed he was fortunate to have employment in the city said, “Most people who live in Chandannagar, if they are not connected to any business like shops or services here, they go to work in Kolkata. In the future, I don't know if the youth will continue to remain here. In my generation, my friends and I have seen them try for jobs in surrounding areas like Kolkata. Of course, unemployment is a problem nowadays, which is not specific to our city. That you understand.”

The respondents unanimously agree that the lack of youth opportunities is not one that is limited or specific to Chandannagar, rather it is a state-wide, or even a nation-wide, issue that requires a systemic change. In this context, many had pointed to the numerous schools and colleges available in the small city. The 2011 census data also shows that the average literacy rate of Chandannagar Municipal Corporation is 89.66%, which is higher than the West Bengal state average of 76.26%. Male literacy stands at 92.38% and female literacy at 86.90%. The situation is not so optimistic when it comes to data regarding the working population of Chandannagar, reflecting the anxieties of unemployment that came up in interviews.

According to the Census of India 2011, Chandannagar Municipal Corporation had a total population of 166,867, of which only 60,208 individuals were engaged in work or business activities, while the remaining 106,659 were classified as non-workers. This indicates that only about 36.1% of the total population participated in economic activity, whereas a significant majority—approximately 63.9%—fell into the non-working category. Within the working population, the vast majority (90.42%) were main workers, engaged in sustained employment, while a smaller proportion (9.58%) were marginal workers with intermittent or seasonal work.

The relatively high share of non-workers reflects the combined presence of dependents such as children and the elderly, as well as a large segment of the population—particularly women—whose labour remains outside formal economic classification. However, overall, the data highlights a limited workforce participation rate in Chandannagar, pointing to both demographic factors and structural constraints within the local economy.

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The gendered pattern of work participation in Chandannagar reveals a stark disparity between male and female economic engagement, with approximately 58.5% of men participating in work compared to only 13.4% of women. From the perspective of feminist economics, this gap cannot be understood merely as women's absence from the labour force, but rather as a reflection of how "work" itself is defined and measured. As Marilyn Waring argues, national accounting systems systematically exclude unpaid domestic and care labour, thereby rendering a significant portion of women's productive activity invisible (Waring).

In Chandannagar, this invisibility is reflected in the disproportionately high share of women classified as "non-workers," despite their likely engagement in essential household and caregiving roles.

Unlike metropolitan centres, smaller urban formations such as Chandannagar often exhibit hybrid socio-economic structures, where traditional gender norms coexist with uneven processes of urbanisation and economic change. As Ananya Roy notes, urbanisation in such contexts is a deeply uneven process shaped by informality and unequal access to resources (Roy). For women in small cities, this often translates into constrained entry into formal labour markets, even as they remain central to sustaining urban households through unpaid work. In small-city contexts like Chandannagar, where public infrastructure for care may be limited, the burden of such labour is disproportionately borne by women, restricting their participation in paid employment.

The stacked gender distribution of workers and non-workers thus reflects both labour market exclusion and infrastructural constraints. Indian feminist economists such as Devaki Jain have similarly highlighted how women's work in non-metropolitan settings is often informal, home-based, or subsistence-oriented, and therefore undercounted in official statistics (Jain).

Image: Gender Distribution of Working Population in Chandannagar Municipal Corporation, 2011. The chart illustrates the proportion of male and female workers among the total working population. Source: Census of India 2011, Primary Census Abstract (PCA), Chandannagar Municipal Corporation, West Bengal.

Image: Workers and Non-Workers by Gender in Chandannagar Municipal Corporation, 2011. The chart compares the absolute number of workers and non-workers among males and females. Source: Census of India 2011, Primary Census Abstract (PCA), Chandannagar Municipal Corporation, West Bengal.

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One of the most significant consequences of the overall dearth of employment opportunities in Chandannagar itself is the pressure to migrate—either to larger cities or abroad—in search of better opportunities. While migration offers individual advancement, it also produces a “brain drain” effect, weakening local social and economic networks and reducing intergenerational continuity within families and businesses. Leaving is also normalised.

Another youth working in his father’s factory responded, “It's not that there aren't any [jobs]. Many factories need engineers. For instance, at my place, there are a few people doing CAD design. Even for lights, coding is needed now. Salaries are much lower compared to Kolkata, though. And apart from factories, there are schools, banks, offices, etc. But if someone is highly educated, they usually go outside. Kolkata is only an hour away. It's not a big deal.” An elderly respondent sighed, “There are no boys left in this neighbourhood, no young men.”

In the absence of structured opportunities, some respondents express concern about youth turning to unproductive or risky behaviours—loitering, substance use, or involvement in minor conflicts. While not universally observed, this perception contributes to broader moral anxiety. Youth disengagement is highly visible in public discourse because it is often expressed through behaviour—gathering in public spaces, perceived idleness, or participation in informal activities. Even the overabundance of totos, an issue raised by many residents, may have been caused by rising unemployment in the formal sector, forcing youth to seek employment through these means.

At the same time, the structural causes—limited employment opportunities, lack of institutional support—are less visible but persist over time. This concern persists because there is a mismatch between rising aspirations (driven by education and exposure) and the availability of local opportunities, combined with insufficient platforms for constructive engagement.

Across the interviews, several interconnected patterns emerge that cut across individual concerns and reveal deeper structural dynamics shaping life in the city:

1. Normalisation of Systemic Gaps

One of the most striking patterns is the normalisation of dysfunction. Whether in infrastructure, healthcare, traffic, or governance, residents no longer expect systems to function efficiently. Instead, they anticipate delays, breakdowns, and gaps—and adapt accordingly. This adaptation takes the form of private solutions (seeking healthcare elsewhere, relying on informal transport, using personal networks), which in turn reduces pressure on public systems and allows these gaps to persist.

2. Aspiration–Reality Mismatch

Particularly evident in discussions around youth, there is a clear mismatch between rising aspirations and limited local opportunities. Education and exposure have expanded expectations, but the city's economic and institutional structures have not evolved at the same pace. This produces frustration, underemployment, and ultimately, outmigration.

3. Exit as a Structural Response

Migration—whether daily commuting to nearby urban centres or permanent relocation—is not seen as exceptional but as necessary. The city is increasingly perceived as a place of upbringing rather than long-term growth. This pattern connects youth concerns, economic stagnation, and the erosion of intergenerational continuity.

4. Fragmentation with Episodic Cohesion

While everyday social life is marked by fragmentation and reduced interaction, community events like Jagaddhatri Puja temporarily restore a sense of unity. This creates a paradox: strong collective identity during festivals, but weak sustained community engagement otherwise.

5. Commercialisation

Commercialisation is not limited to heritage spaces—it extends to cultural practices, public spaces, and even social life. Festivals become competitive spectacles, traditional businesses are replaced by standardised enterprises, and public spaces are increasingly shaped by economic rather than social priorities.

6. Erosion of Trust in Institutions

Repeated experiences of unresponsiveness—whether in governance, healthcare, or regulation—have led to a broader erosion of trust. Citizens continue to articulate concerns, but with diminishing expectations of resolution. This results in a shift from active engagement to cautious disengagement.

7. Interconnectedness of Concerns

Importantly, no issue exists in isolation. Traffic affects healthcare access; governance gaps exacerbate infrastructure decline; lack of opportunities drives social fragmentation. The interviews reveal a tightly interwoven system of challenges rather than discrete problems.

VOICES OF CONCERN

While concerns are widely shared, they are experienced differently across social groups.

<p>Youth (late teens to 30s)</p>	<p>Primary concern: lack of meaningful employment and growth opportunities Experience: frustration, uncertainty, and pressure to migrate Pattern: disengagement is often structural rather than voluntary Additional dimension: reduced civic participation due to the perceived irrelevance of local systems</p>
<p>Women (across age groups)</p>	<p>Primary concerns: mobility, undervalued labour and access to services Experience: restricted movement, dependence on family or safe transport options Impact: limited participation in formal employment and social life Intersection: safety concerns intensify issues related to infrastructure and traffic disorder</p>
<p>Elderly Residents (60s–70s)</p>	<p>Primary concerns: healthcare access, mobility, and social isolation Experience: increased vulnerability due to weak public systems and declining community support Emotional dimension: strong sense of loss regarding heritage and community life</p>
<p>Working Professionals (30s–50s)</p>	<p>Primary concerns: infrastructure inefficiency, traffic, and governance gaps Experience: time loss, stress, and reduced productivity Adaptation: reliance on private solutions and personal networks</p>
<p>Small Business Owners and Family-Run Establishments</p>	<p>Primary concerns: commercialisation, rising costs, and uncertain succession Experience: economic pressure and fear of closure Long-term issue: breakdown of intergenerational continuity</p>
<p>Lower-Income Groups</p> <p> Nāgrika</p>	<p>Primary concerns: access to healthcare, stable employment, and basic services Experience: disproportionate impact due to inability to access private alternatives Structural position: most affected by systemic failures, least able to adapt</p>

VOICES OF CONCERN

Governance is perceived as reactive rather than proactive, addressing issues only when they become highly visible or urgent. This reinforces a cycle of disillusionment and disengagement. Key complaints include a lack of timely response to civic issues, poor coordination between departments, absence of long-term planning and limited avenues for meaningful citizen participation. Traffic mismanagement is a highly visible manifestation of governance gaps. Weak enforcement of rules, illegal parking and encroachment or lack of pedestrian infrastructure not only disrupt mobility but also signal a broader breakdown of regulatory authority.

The absence of reliable healthcare facilities is framed as a governance failure. Although often implicit, environmental issues surface through, such as waterlogging linked to poor drainage, pollution from traffic congestion, overcrowding during festivals, loss of green or open spaces due to commercialisation, etc. These concerns are rarely articulated in technical terms but are experienced through their everyday effects on health and mobility.

The interviews collectively reveal a city where everyday life is shaped by adaptation to structural limitations. Citizens are not passive—they actively navigate and respond to challenges—but these responses often compensate for, rather than resolve, systemic gaps. At the same time, the persistence and consistency of these concerns indicate that residents remain invested in the city's future.

The key challenge, therefore, lies not only in addressing individual issues but in restoring alignment between institutions and citizen expectations, development and inclusivity, and economic growth and social cohesion. Without this alignment, the city risks deepening cycles of disengagement, outmigration, and fragmentation—even as it continues to grow and transform.

Dreams for Tomorrow

Dreams for Tomorrow

While the interviews foreground multiple anxieties, they also reveal a clear, grounded vision of what residents want the city to become. These aspirations are not utopian; they are practical, shaped by lived experience, and often framed in terms of improvement rather than transformation. Citizens are not asking for a radically different city—they are asking for a functional, inclusive, and sustaining one that allows them to live, work, and belong with dignity. Residents want a city where basic systems—roads, drainage, transport—work predictably. The aspiration is not for large-scale modernisation, but for consistency and reliability in everyday life. These are seen as solvable issues, not structural impossibilities. Residents often note that improvements have occurred in the past, suggesting that change is achievable with sustained effort. A citizen historian noted, “A primary condition for improvement is having good roads and a proper system for controlling vehicles. I won't say that's not happening at all, but how lasting is it? After a road is repaired once, if it doesn't last even a year, then what happens? The Corporation's expenses increase.” This hope can remain alive if maintenance becomes continuous rather than reactive, and accountability mechanisms are strengthened.

A strong aspiration is for nearby, reliable healthcare facilities, particularly for emergencies. People want assurance that critical care is accessible without needing to leave the city. A doctor shared that in his experience, “people, especially if they have even a little money, have no trust in Chandannagar’s healthcare facilities. The sub-divisional hospital is quite a big facility, and there are numerous private nursing homes. But the thing is, I cannot blame them because the medical facilities available here are not adequate in many cases.” The presence of smaller clinics indicates an existing foundation that could be expanded or upgraded. This hope can remain alive if investment prioritises strengthening local healthcare infrastructure and emergency services.

Residents hope for a city where young people can build their futures locally, rather than being compelled to leave. This includes better jobs, skill development, and support for entrepreneurship. There is recognition that the city already has educational institutions and some industries, suggesting growth potential. A municipal representative suggested: “In our area, in Chandannagar, there's a world-famous light industry – Chandannagar’s festival lighting. If, through the government, some technical training in the electrical field, with new technologies, can be provided to the children. And if the government can arrange some very easy loans from this sector, then I think this area of Chandannagar will engage more in the electrical business. Then this area will become much more financially self-reliant. And the more financially self-reliant they become, the more the children will improve our social environment. I think that the environment will be good. Everyone will improve it.” There have been some initiatives towards implementing this hope already in the city, with the government-sponsored Alo light hub, which is supposed to function as a training workshop for light artists. There have been efforts implemented by colleges as well.

DREAMS FOR TOMORROW

A professor of Khalisani Mahavidyalaya stated, “In our college, we have held discussions with companies such as TCS and Airtel so that they can conduct campus recruitment. For three consecutive years, TCS has recruited non-technical staff from our non-technical college, and they will conduct campus recruitment again this year. We have also organised separate classes on interview preparation and skill development. We have observed significant student interest in these initiatives. Compared to nearby colleges, our student enrollment has been relatively good this year, likely because of these efforts. The idea that studying here can lead to job opportunities has taken root among students, and some serious students are making good use of this.”

Many young respondents were themselves sceptical about their opportunities in the city, but constrained their hopes for the city, citing the implausibility of large-scale industry or government sector offices being constructed here. Instead, they admit to having resigned themselves to ultimately having to leave or at least commute to Kolkata. While many respondents noted that the city provided a living to anyone who worked hard, a dearth of jobs for educated or specialised youth seemed visible. The hope then becomes one for sustainable long-term employment opportunities in the formal sector. This hope can remain alive if local economies are strengthened and linked more effectively to education and skills.

Citizens do not reject development, but they want it to be balanced with preservation. The aspiration is for a city that grows without losing its identity. The people still cling to this hope because heritage still exists—it has not yet been completely erased, and can still be protected. Residents acknowledged recent efforts by citizens and authorities to preserve some heritage, for example, in the establishment of the Chandernagore College Museum, which, in contrast to the Duplex Museum, which holds the French legacy, provides a glimpse into the history of ordinary people's lives. A young active citizen confessed, “It felt proud to see the revolutionary history of the city represented in concrete form. I, personally, being a student of Kanailal Vidyamandir, spent a long time reading and experiencing the history of Kanailal Dutta. It felt like a proud moment of celebration.”

They, however, ascertain that more can certainly be done. A young school teacher said about the issue: “If the entire city of Chandannagar could be showcased anew, or the many places in the city that revolutionaries used, or can be called revolutionaries' houses. They stayed there once. Those houses are now dilapidated. Those houses should also be repaired and nicely developed, I think. It would probably be a good thing for the residents of Chandannagar.” Another citizen historian highlighted the city as a potential site for heritage tourism that has not yet been properly utilised. A government official acknowledged the recent development of Alo, a West Bengal tourism department property, to act as a stay for the entire colonial circuit, including Chandannagar, Chinsurah, Bandel, Srerampore, etc. This hope can remain alive if planning frameworks integrate heritage conservation into development policies.

DREAMS FOR TOMORROW

Many residents, however, see Chandannagar as overpopulated, with the current infrastructure unable to support more. Reactions to migrants and settlers are varied: while some residents categorise Chandannagar as welcoming, others are sceptical. The commercial development of the city also feels stifling, especially to older residents, while many younger respondents praised the convenience. A doctor and hobbyist gardener hoped that no new apartment buildings would be constructed in the city in the near future. Highlighting the self-sufficiency and social importance of the older bazaars like Laxmiganj bazar and Bowbazar, he framed newer commercial development as redundant and unnecessary. He echoed the sentiments of a student who enjoys the quieter and more natural parts of the city's outskirts and does not want to see more concrete houses in the name of development there. A senior citizen who had moved to the city recently also said: "I don't want more and more houses, no need for houses. Let the ponds remain, that's good. There's a pond here; if you look carefully through this window, you can see it. That means the environment is sufficiently green." Some, however, raised issues like pollution.

The same nature-enjoying student said, "There's a lot of pollution. All kinds, air, water, land, noise, even light. If you have been to that side (across the rail tracks) you will automatically notice the temperature difference. About 4-5 degrees easily. Why? Because this side has become overpopulated and congested. Pollution followed." A former councillor raised an alarming issue about pollution in his area. According to him, the drainage system in his area is so constructed that dirty water from the drains is routed through open ponds, leading to unhygienic and dangerous conditions. A hope for better pollution control can remain alive because the authorities have already implemented successful plans like the door-to-door waste collection, relocating the Bhagar landfill, recycling means and so on. And the hope for the pause in "development" with new construction of residential or commercial properties may remain alive if stricter land use regulations are passed and enforced.

Image: Busts of freedom fighters hailing from Chandannagar, including Arabinda Ghosh and Kanailal Dutta, at the Chandannagar College Museum

DREAMS FOR TOMORROW

Citizens want to feel heard and see tangible outcomes from their participation. This is believed to be possible because residents continue to engage—filing complaints, attending meetings—indicating residual trust. Most residents agreed that the people of Chandannagar are quite active on social media and voice their concerns frequently. Many, however, do not see the benefit of such social media activism as they fail to see any real impact arising from such movements. Rather, they want clearer and formal modes of addressing their problems. This hope can remain alive if citizen feedback mechanisms are strengthened and made transparent.

Residents hope for a return—not necessarily to the past—but to a form of active community engagement, where relationships extend beyond immediate households. People believe it is possible because moments of strong community—such as during Jagaddhatri Puja—still exist. This hope can remain alive if spaces and opportunities for regular interaction are actively created and supported.

Citizens aspire to a city where rules are followed and enforced, particularly in traffic and public space usage. The rules already exist—the issue is enforcement, not absence. This hope can remain alive if consistent enforcement replaces selective or occasional action.

Comparison to other cities, including Kolkata, which is the closest metro city to Chandannagar, inevitably came up again and again over the interviews. A pattern that emerged over many interviews was the quiet and often unnoticed adjustment that the residents had made in their daily lives: their reliance on Kolkata. Most residents did not think it was an adjustment at all, because commuting to the city is convenient enough, but some respondents raised their hopes to be less reliant on Kolkata for needs like healthcare, education, jobs, cultural needs and other opportunities.

Image: A traffic sign at the GT Road-Rashbehari Avenue intersection

DREAMS FOR TOMORROW

In 2014, the State government proposed that Bansberia, Hooghly-Chinsurah, Uttarpara-Kotrung, Serampore, Rishra, Konnagar, Champdani, Chandannagar and Bhadreswar would be clubbed together under the Chandannagar Municipal Corporation (AITC Official). The idea was that a bigger municipality or municipal corporation would allow larger budgets and bigger projects in these cities. However, the plan did not come to pass. As a councillor serving during that time pointed out, while there were pros to having a bigger combined municipality, the unique needs of each of these cities would go unnoticed. He gave the example of Chandannagar, which, being one of the strongholds of France during the colonial era, still receives some aid from the French government. Such aid, in the form of research grants and heritage preservation projects, is for the use of the former colony only, and would not benefit cities like, say, Bansberia. Still, it would figure in the city budget and therefore pose a budgetary nightmare.

The hope of the residents of Chandannagar, therefore, is not always a bigger city, but one that is mindful of its own unique needs. This hope can remain alive if the authorities and the residents work together to preserve and enhance the uniqueness of the city rather than diluting and homogenising it with general urbanity.

Taken together, these aspirations point toward a city that is functional, inclusive, economically viable, and socially cohesive. Residents are not asking for a rapid or dramatic transformation, but for a steady alignment between systems and needs. What emerges is a desire for a city where everyday life is predictable, opportunities are accessible, and community remains meaningful.

For these hopes to materialise, several changes are necessary. At the level of systems, there is a need for stronger infrastructure, better healthcare integration, and more coordinated governance. At the level of behaviour, both citizens and institutions must engage more consistently with rules, responsibilities, and collective processes. At the level of mindset, there must be a shift from reactive responses to proactive planning, and from viewing heritage and community as secondary concerns to recognising them as integral to development.

In the short term, several changes appear both practical and feasible within a five-year horizon. These include improved maintenance of roads and drainage, more consistent traffic regulation, upgrading existing healthcare facilities, and introducing local skill development programs.

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However, bigger structural changes require longer timelines and broader coordination. These include diversifying the local economy to create sustainable employment, building robust healthcare infrastructure, and developing integrated urban planning frameworks that balance growth with preservation.

Such transformations require the involvement of multiple actors, including local authorities, state-level institutions, and civic bodies. Citizens also play a role, but their participation cannot substitute for systemic reform. Small interventions and long-term transformation must operate together. Immediate improvements can build trust and demonstrate responsiveness, while structural reforms ensure sustainability. Citizens themselves are seen as active participants in this process. The interviews suggest a willingness to engage, comply with regulations, and contribute to community life. At the same time, there is a clear recognition that citizen effort alone cannot compensate for institutional shortcomings.

The gap between present realities and future aspirations is shaped by several barriers. Institutional inertia remains a major obstacle, with systems that exist but fail to function efficiently or consistently. Planning processes are often fragmented, addressing issues in isolation rather than as interconnected challenges. Resource constraints and prioritisation issues further slow progress, particularly in critical areas such as healthcare and employment. Equally significant is the normalisation of dysfunction. As residents adapt to systemic gaps, the urgency for change diminishes, allowing these conditions to persist.

The erosion of trust in governance also reduces civic engagement, weakening collective pressure for reform. Finally, structural economic limitations constrain the city's ability to generate opportunities, particularly for youth.

Despite these challenges, the interviews suggest that hope persists because it is grounded in realism. Residents do not imagine a grand and idealised future; they envision a city that simply works better, more fairly, and more consistently. The central challenge, therefore, is not the absence of vision, but the absence of alignment.

Bridging this gap requires reconnecting aspiration with opportunity, governance with accountability, and growth with inclusivity. Only then can the city become a place where residents are not forced to choose between staying and succeeding, but are able to do both.

Policy Insights

Policy Insights

1. Mobility, Accessibility, and Traffic Regulation

Mobility challenges emerge consistently across interviews, not only in terms of poor infrastructure but also weak regulation. Citizens experience roads as congested, poorly maintained, and informally managed spaces. Traffic rules exist but are inconsistently enforced, and pedestrian infrastructure is inadequate. This affects access to work, education, healthcare, and public life—particularly for the elderly and daily wage earners. The issue reflects a gap not in policy absence, but in implementation and coordination. Existing urban transport schemes and traffic management frameworks are not effectively adapted to the city’s scale and mixed-use character.

Immediate improvements can focus on enforcement and maintenance. Regular deployment of traffic personnel at key junctions, strict action against illegal parking, and restoration of non-functional traffic signals can significantly improve flow. Low-cost interventions such as repainting road markings and installing signage can enhance both safety and predictability.

A coordinated traffic management plan is needed, integrating different modes of transport—autos, e-rickshaws, pedestrians, and private vehicles. This could include designated parking zones, regulated stands for informal transport, and pedestrian-friendly crossings. Leveraging state-level urban mobility programs and integrating them with local needs would be critical.

Over time, mobility planning must shift toward integrated urban design, where roads are not treated as isolated corridors but as shared public infrastructure. This requires alignment between municipal bodies, traffic police, and urban development authorities, alongside sustained budget allocation for maintenance rather than one-time upgrades.

Stakeholders: Municipal authorities, traffic police, urban development departments, local transport unions, and resident groups.

2. Healthcare Access and Local Service Provision

Healthcare inadequacy is a critical concern, particularly in emergencies. While smaller clinics exist, there is no dependable, well-equipped facility within accessible distance. This forces residents to travel to larger cities, creating delays, financial strain, and risk. The issue reflects a gap in healthcare planning and service integration, where primary care exists but is not connected to emergency and advanced care systems.

Strengthening existing primary health centres with better staffing, availability of essential medicines, and diagnostic facilities can improve access. Establishing reliable ambulance services and emergency response protocols would address critical gaps. Currently, the councillors and municipal authorities run ambulance services that residents can avail but most operate through informal systems.

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Upgrading selected facilities into well-equipped community health centres can provide a middle tier of care. Partnerships with private providers under existing public health schemes can improve service delivery. The recent partnership of Ankur Hospital in Bhadreswar, the neighbouring city, with the reputed Charnock Hospital group gives new hope to many. Awareness and effective implementation of state and national health insurance schemes can reduce financial burden.

The city requires integration into a regional healthcare network, ensuring that advanced care facilities are accessible within critical timeframes. This involves coordinated planning at the state level, sustained investment, and regulatory oversight to ensure quality and affordability.

Stakeholders: State health department, municipal health authorities, private healthcare providers, insurance scheme administrators, and community health workers

3. Local Economy, Youth Opportunities, and Livelihood Sustainability

A major structural challenge is the mismatch between rising aspirations and limited local opportunities. While small industries and businesses exist, they do not offer sufficient scale, income, or diversity to retain educated youth. This leads to outmigration, weakening both the local economy and social continuity. At the same time, family-run businesses face pressure from commercialisation and lack institutional support.

Skill development programs aligned with local economic needs can improve employability. Career counselling and placement support within educational institutions can help bridge the transition from education to work. Encouraging local entrepreneurship through small grants or simplified registration processes can provide immediate support.

Developing local economic clusters—such as small-scale manufacturing, services, or cultural industries—can create more stable employment. Linking existing government skill development schemes with local industries can improve outcomes. Support for small businesses through credit access, tax relief, or market linkages can strengthen existing economic structures. For example, the lightmaking industry, which generates employment throughout the city, can stand to benefit from such support. The Alo light hub, inaugurated in 2021, had promised to fulfil these dreams, but many remain dissatisfied with its execution (“Alo Hub Opens...”).

A diversified local economy requires strategic planning and investment, potentially integrating the city into broader regional economic corridors. Policies must also address the sustainability of family-run enterprises, recognising them as both economic and cultural assets. Stakeholders: State industry departments, municipal authorities, educational institutions, local businesses, financial institutions, and entrepreneurship support organisations.

4. Heritage, Public Spaces, and Cultural Infrastructure

The erosion of heritage and transformation of community spaces reflect a lack of integration between development and cultural preservation. Long-standing establishments and historically significant spaces are being replaced without adequate regulatory oversight. At the same time, public spaces for everyday interaction are diminishing. This indicates a gap in urban planning frameworks, where cultural infrastructure is not treated as essential.

Documentation and identification of key heritage sites and traditional establishments can be initiated. Temporary measures, such as regulating encroachments and improving maintenance of public spaces, can enhance usability.

Introducing local guidelines for heritage-sensitive development can help balance growth with preservation. Incentives for maintaining or restoring historic properties can encourage compliance. Revitalisation of public spaces—parks, community centres, and waterfronts—can strengthen social life.

Heritage conservation must be embedded within formal planning processes, with clear regulatory mechanisms and dedicated funding. Cultural events like Jagaddhatri Puja can be supported not only as spectacles but as community-building platforms, ensuring broader participation.

Stakeholders: Municipal planning bodies, heritage conservation authorities, local cultural organisations, business owners, and community groups.

5. Governance, Civic Participation, and Service Delivery

A cross-cutting concern is the gap between citizens and governance systems. Residents report a lack of responsiveness, poor follow-through, and limited avenues for meaningful participation. This affects not only trust but also the effectiveness of service delivery across sectors. The issue lies in institutional processes and accountability mechanisms, rather than the absence of governance structures.

Strengthening grievance redressal systems—through clear timelines, tracking mechanisms, and public communication—can improve responsiveness. Regular ward-level meetings and accessible communication channels can enhance engagement. According to The West Bengal Municipal (Ward Committee) Rules, 2001, a ward committee must be constituted for each ward after a general election. The Committee must meet at least once per month and have annual general meetings with all residents of the ward. While the formal policy exists, residents as well as councillors identified a gap in its actual implementation.

POLICY INSIGHTS

Digitisation of services and complaint systems can improve transparency and efficiency. Capacity building within municipal departments can enhance coordination and implementation. Public awareness campaigns can encourage citizen participation and compliance.

Institutionalising participatory governance—through formal mechanisms for citizen consultation in planning and budgeting—can rebuild trust. This requires policy commitment and cultural change within governance systems, emphasising accountability and inclusivity.

Stakeholders: Municipal authorities, elected representatives, state government departments, civil society organisations, and residents.

6. Implementation Deficit and Maintenance Culture

A recurring pattern across infrastructure, healthcare, traffic, and public spaces is not the absence of schemes, but the absence of sustained implementation and maintenance. Citizens repeatedly point out that systems are built or introduced, but not maintained, monitored, or followed through. This indicates a governance model oriented toward one-time interventions rather than lifecycle management.

Routine maintenance schedules for roads, drainage, and public facilities, with publicly visible timelines, should be introduced. Additionally, simple audit mechanisms at the ward level to track whether basic services are functioning should allow smoother cooperation between residents and authorities. Shifting budget allocation toward maintenance funds, not just capital expenditure, or introducing performance-linked contracts for service providers (e.g., waste management, road repair), ensuring accountability beyond initial completion can help curb these issues.

Institutionalise a maintenance-first governance model, where every new project includes a funded and monitored maintenance plan. This requires changes in budgeting practices and administrative incentives.

Stakeholders: Municipal engineering departments, finance departments, contractors, ward committees, and residents.

7. Inequality of Access and Everyday Exclusion

While many issues appear universal, the data show that their impact is unevenly distributed. Access to healthcare, mobility, employment, and safety varies significantly across class, gender, and age. This reveals a gap between service provision and equitable access.

Identifying high-vulnerability groups (elderly, women, low-income residents) and prioritising service delivery in those areas—such as better lighting, safer transport access, and targeted healthcare outreach will ensure equity.

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Integrating inclusivity audits into urban planning will ensure that infrastructure projects consider accessibility, safety, and affordability. Moreover, strengthening the implementation of existing welfare schemes by improving awareness and last-mile delivery will ensure that the services actually reach those who need them the most.

Embedding equity as a planning principle may ensure that all major policies and projects are evaluated for their impact on different social groups. This requires institutional capacity and data-driven decision-making.

Stakeholders: Municipal bodies, social welfare departments, women's groups, community organisations, and public health agencies.

8. Informality as a Parallel System

The interviews reveal that much of the city operates through informal systems—from transport (e-rickshaws, autos) to employment and even service delivery. These systems fill critical gaps but remain poorly regulated. Rather than eliminating informality, the challenge is to recognise and integrate it into formal planning.

The first step is to map and recognise informal systems—such as transport routes and vendor zones—to understand their role in the urban ecosystem. Further interventions would include introducing designated spaces for vendors, licensing frameworks for informal transport, and basic safety standards. This improves order without disrupting livelihoods.

At a more holistic level, developing a hybrid governance model that integrates informal systems into formal urban planning ensures both efficiency and livelihood protection.

Stakeholders: Municipal authorities, transport departments, informal worker unions, vendor associations, and local police.

Image: Mary field

Conclusion

Taken together, these structural issues reveal a city where the primary challenge is not the absence of systems, but the misalignment between provision, access, and sustained functioning. Across sectors, citizens are not pointing to a lack of schemes or initiatives. Instead, they highlight how existing systems remain unevenly implemented, poorly maintained, or inaccessible to certain groups. Roads are built but not maintained, healthcare facilities exist but are not dependable, economic activity is present but does not translate into stable opportunity, and governance structures function without consistently engaging citizens. Informal systems step in to fill these gaps, but without integration, they introduce new challenges of regulation and equity.

What emerges is a pattern where short-term fixes substitute for long-term reliability, and where individual adaptation compensates for systemic gaps. This is compounded by uneven access, where the ability to navigate or bypass these shortcomings depends on class, gender, and mobility. As a result, the city functions, but not equitably or predictably. At the same time, the interviews make clear that these issues are deeply interconnected. Mobility affects access to healthcare and employment; weak governance undermines infrastructure and service delivery; lack of opportunity drives outmigration, which in turn affects local economies and community continuity. Informality, cultural practices, and everyday adaptations sustain the city—but also mask the extent of systemic strain.

The policy challenge, therefore, is not to introduce entirely new frameworks, but to strengthen the coherence, continuity, and inclusivity of what already exists. This requires shifting from a model of reactive intervention to one of integrated, maintenance-oriented, and equity-focused governance, where systems are designed not just to be created, but to function reliably over time and across social groups. Ultimately, the question is not whether the city can grow, but whether it can function consistently, include all its residents, and retain its social and economic vitality. Addressing this requires aligning infrastructure, services, and governance processes with the lived realities of citizens—so that the burden of making the city work does not fall disproportionately on those who inhabit it.

Image: The iconic Joraghat on a wintry morning

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Message from the Founders

Ten years ago, we set off on a journey across India's small towns. Over five months and fifty cities, we came through stories, crafts, silences, and dreams. We rediscovered that our smaller cities were not merely settlements; they were living archives of collective memory and identity—fossils of space and time inhabited by breath and imagination.

In Ratnagiri we were directed by many city experts to meet an auto mechanic. He was the go-to person for everyone in the city, including the city government, for engineering issues such as the city's water supply. He had seen the city evolve and remembered its various extensions, its water supply networks, and the various issues the city had faced in the last few decades. In Thanjavur, we sat with a veena-maker working 20-hour days in a modest shed, carving centuries of musical tradition into a single piece of jackfruit wood. We listened to bakers, poets, priests, and students. They told us not only what their cities were, but what they could become.

What struck us most was this: citizens carry the city's soul. The insights they hold—about its past, its present, and its future—are powerful, yet rarely represented in how cities are imagined or governed. This realization gave genesis to the Nāgrika Fellowship. It has been our attempt to honour the power of local voices—to create space for young people to observe, listen, document, and co-create city narratives from within. Each City Vision Document is not just a reflection of one fellow's journey; it's a collaborative act of remembering and imagining.

We hope this document stirs dialogue, ownership, and pride. And just like cities that shape their people, we hope this fellowship shapes a new kind of citizen—curious, rooted, and ready to lead.

We exist to ensure small-city voices, often unheard, have the knowledge and tools to influence the development and policies of their communities.

We focus on citizen-driven research. By engaging directly with small city communities, we present their authentic realities, untouched by outside narratives. This hands-on approach keeps small city voices at the heart of everything we do.

Citizen-Centred

It's always about the people. Small-city citizens are at the heart of everything we do.

Curious and Objective

Our approach stems from curiosity—focusing on the truth, making sure every voice in small cities is heard clearly and fairly.

Credible and Rooted

We are committed to producing knowledge and insight from the small cities that is dependable and high-quality.

Resourceful

We make the most of what we have, using our resources wisely to create valuable knowledge.

Small Cities, Big Love

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GLOSSARY & LOCAL TERMS

TABLE 1: GLOSSARY & LOCAL TERMS	
Word or Phrase in Regional Language	Translation in English
<i>Barowari</i>	Neighbourhood community
<i>Chalchitro</i>	traditional, rounded background frame of idols for puja
<i>Chand</i>	Moon
<i>Chand Sadagar</i>	A sea merchant of Champaknagar who is one of the principal characters in the Bengali medieval poem "Manasamangal Kāvya" (or "Manasa Vijay") written by Bipradas Pipulai
<i>Chandan</i>	White sandalwood
<i>Chandi</i>	A demon-destroying form of the Hindu goddess Shakti, particularly popular in eastern India. She is known by various names, such as Mahamaya ("Great Magic") or Abhaya ("She Who Is Without Fear"). Her representation is similar to that of Durga, another form of Shakti. She is shown with either 8 or 10 arms, seated on a lion vehicle. Hundreds of folktales and songs tell of her exploits. She is the central figure of an extensive medieval Bengali literature known as Chandi-mangal, the most famous of which is that of Mukundarama Chakravarti (c. 16th century). (source: Brittanica)
<i>Chaulpatty</i>	Grain market
<i>Dashami</i>	Literally "tenth." The tenth day of any Hindu luni-solar calendar month. Here, on Dashami, the city bids farewell to the Goddess. The day is defined by the grand immersion procession of Chandannagar, a spectacular parade of art, light, and devotion, symbolising the Goddess's return to her abode.
<i>Ekadashi</i>	Literally "eleventh." Here, the day